

Aristotle's square for mining fuzzy concepts

Stefania Boffa^{a,*,*}, Petra Murinová^b

^a IULM University, Dipartimento di Business, Diritto, Economia e Consumi, Faculty of Communication, 20143 Milan, Italy

^b University of Ostrava, Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling, NSC IT4Innovations, 30. dubna 22, 701 03 Ostrava 1, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Aristotle's square
Formal concept analysis
Fuzzy formal context
Fuzzy formal concepts
Fuzzy relational concept analysis
Fuzzy relational context family
Relations of opposition
Fuzzy scaling quantifiers

ABSTRACT

Aristotle's Square also known as *Square of Opposition*, is a mathematical diagram dating back to Greek philosophy and exhibiting the connection between four logical propositions in a simple graphical form. *Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis* (FRCA) is a technique for extracting special clusters called *fuzzy concepts* from a *Fuzzy Relational Context Family* (FRCF), which is a dataset organized as multiple fuzzy object-attribute and object-object relations. The primary FRCA tools to obtain information from data are special fuzzy quantifiers viewed as interpretations in a model of formulas of the *formal theory of the intermediate generalized quantifiers*. This work focuses on the issue of generating a collection of fuzzy concepts from a certain FRCF, by choosing one of four particular FRCA quantifiers: the *positive universal quantifier* S_1 , the *negative universal quantifier* S_1^- , the *positive existential quantifier* S_3 , and the *negative existential quantifier* S_3^- . Certainly, the selection of the quantifier is crucial in the FRCA procedure since it affects the final concept classification: diverse fuzzy concepts arise from varying quantifiers. As the initial objective, this article introduces the logical relations involving S_1 , S_1^- , S_3 , and S_3^- , in order to arrange them in a graded version of the Aristotelian square. The second goal of this study is to examine the connections among fuzzy concepts produced by distinct quantifiers in $\{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$. Therefore, our findings provide a twofold contribution to the advancement of Aristotle's square. Indeed, they reveal a novel interpretation of the square of opposition within the framework of Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis, emphasizing its potential as a valuable tool for the analysis of data.

1. Introduction

Aristotle's Square also known as *Square of Opposition*, is a mathematical diagram dating back to Greek philosophy and widely examined through propositional logic [1,2] and classical first-order logic [3,4]. It graphically represents the relationship between the statements A: "all A's are B", E: "all A's are not B's", I: "at least one in A is in B", and O: "at least one A is not a B" [5]. As shown in Fig. 1, the following logical relations characterize the Aristotelian square:

- A and E are *contraries*, i.e. they cannot be true together, but they both can be false;
- A and I are *subalterns* as well as E and O, i.e. A implies I and E implies O;
- I and O are *sub-contraries*, i.e. they cannot be false together, but they both can be true;
- A and O are *contradictories* as well as E and I, i.e. A is the negation of O and E is the negation of I.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: stefania.boffa@iulm.it (S. Boffa).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fss.2025.109323>

Received 15 March 2024; Received in revised form 6 December 2024; Accepted 16 February 2025

Available online 21 February 2025

0165-0114/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Aristotle's square. The lines —, ····, →, = denote that the corresponding logical propositions are contraries, contradictories, subalterns, and sub-contraries, respectively.

The construction of Aristotle's square involves the concept of *existential import* or *presupposition*, corresponding to the assumption that the universe of quantification must be non-empty [6]. The square of opposition has been generalized in more complex figures, such as hexagons [7,8], octagons [9,10], and cubes [11,12], where additional propositions along with their related logical relations are considered. Then, the Aristotelian square and its extensions represent useful charts to illustrate the connections between concepts in various scenarios, so they have been repurposed in many fields like Rough set Theory [13], Formal Concept Analysis [14], Probability Theory [15], Possibility Theory [16], and Three-way Decision Theory [17,18]. Moreover, throughout the past century, scholars have explored these types of structures in many-valued logic [19–22]. Finally, in [23,24], graded versions of polygons, cubes, and extended cubes have been investigated in Fuzzy Formal Concept Analysis. In this article, we construct graded Aristotle's squares, where the vertices are predicates interpreted by fuzzy relations.

Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis (FRCA) is one of the generalizations of *Formal Concept Analysis (FCA)*, which is a mathematical theory to classify and analyze data. FCA was introduced by Wille to mathematically describe the philosophical significance of concepts [25–27], finding applications in various research fields (see [28–31] for some recent examples). FCA mines a collection of special clusters called *formal concepts* from a given *formal context*, which is a dataset made of a set of objects, a set of attributes, and a crisp relation between objects and attributes. A formal concept is a pair (A, B) where “ A is the set of all objects having all attributes of B ” and “ B is the set of all attributes satisfied by all objects of A ”. According to the tradition, A and B are respectively named *extent* and *intent* of the concept [32].

Fuzzy Formal Concept Analysis (FFCA) extends FCA with fuzzy logic, to obtain information in the form of *fuzzy concepts* from *fuzzy formal contexts*, where an attribute is assigned to an object with a certain degree of the real interval $[0,1]$. Thus, a fuzzy formal context is represented by a triple (X, Y, I) , where X is a set of objects, Y is a set of attributes, and $I : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a fuzzy relation between objects and attributes. Fuzzy concepts can be defined starting from diverse approaches existing in the literature. In this article, we consider a *one-sided threshold* method for deriving fuzzy concepts, which was introduced and studied in [33,34]. In this case, a fuzzy concept (A, B) is composed of a fuzzy set of objects A and a crisp set of attributes B , which are connected through a pair of operators F_I and G_I depending on a threshold T in $(0,1)$, which determines what truth degrees are sufficiently high in the initial fuzzy formal context to be considered. As an example, we can suppose that $T = 0.6$, X is a set of students, Y is a set of skills, and let $x \in X$ and let $y \in Y$, $I(x, y)$ is the truth degree to which “the student x has the skill y ”; a fuzzy concept (A, B) where $A = \{0.7/Alice, 0.8/Bob\}$ and $B = \{calculations, problem - solving\}$ carries the following information: “Alice and Bob are all students of X who are good at both calculations and problem-solving with a truth degree of at least 0.6”; “Alice is good at both calculations and problem-solving with a truth degree of at least 0.7”; “Bob is good at both calculations and problem-solving with a truth degree of at least 0.8”; “calculations and problem-solving are both Y skills shared by Alice and Bob with a truth degree of at least 0.6”.

Relational Concept Analysis (RCA) constructs conceptual structures expanding the FCA purpose since it deals with different object categories and links between these objects [35,36]. RCA applications include ontology learning [37–39], software engineering [40, 41], medicine [42], and so on.

Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis (FRCA) produces a set of fuzzy concepts from a *Fuzzy Relational Context Family (FRCF)*, which is composed of multiple fuzzy object-attribute and object-object relations [43,44]. FRCA can be considered an extension of both Relational Concept Analysis (RCA integrated with fuzzy logic) and Fuzzy Formal Concept Analysis.

The FRCA process mainly consists of the following steps:

1. Firstly, the given fuzzy relational context family undergoes a transformation to become a collection of fuzzy formal contexts.
2. Secondly, fuzzy concepts are derived from each fuzzy formal context by employing one of the techniques available in the existing literature.

The primary tools for converting a fuzzy context family into a collection of fuzzy formal contexts (i.e. for realizing the first step of the FRCA procedure) are special fuzzy quantifiers, which are based on the Łukasiewicz algebra and are viewed as interpretations in a model of specific formulas of the *formal theory of the intermediate generalized quantifiers* [45]. In this paper, we are interested in four particular FRCA quantifiers: the *positive universal quantifier* S_1 , the *negative universal quantifier* S_1^- , the *positive existential quantifier* S_3 , and the *negative existential quantifier* S_3^- . These are functions assigning a value of the real interval $[0,1]$ to each pair of fuzzy sets of a finite universe X . Their meaning can be readily comprehended through an example. Assume that X is a set of students and A and

B are fuzzy sets of X so that let $x \in X$, $A(x)$ and $B(x)$ are the truth degrees to which “the student x is good at calculations” and “the student x is good at problem-solving”. Thus, the values $S_1(A, B)$, $S_1^-(A, B)$, $S_3(A, B)$, and $S_3^-(A, B)$ respectively express how much

- all students who are good at calculations are also good at problem-solving;
- all students who are good at calculations are not good at problem-solving;
- at least one student is good at both calculations and problem-solving;
- at least one student is good at calculations but not at problem-solving.

Positive and negative quantifiers respectively catch positive and negative information in the initial dataset, i.e. information based on the presence and absence of a certain amount of properties. A larger class of FRCA quantifiers has been introduced in [43] and [44]: *fuzzy scaling quantifiers* are defined using the so-called *evaluative linguistic expressions*, which are expressions of natural language like *very big* and *extremely big* described in a formal system of higher-order fuzzy logic (fuzzy type theory) [46–48]; *t-scaling quantifiers* depend on a threshold of the real interval $[0,1]$. A first comparison between fuzzy scaling and t-scaling quantifiers has been discussed in [49].

This work essentially focuses on the issue of generating a collection of fuzzy concepts from the simplest fuzzy relational context family \mathbf{K} made of a pair of fuzzy formal contexts (X, Y, I) and (Z, W, J) and a fuzzy relation $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ between their objects, by choosing one of the quantifiers among S_1 , S_1^- , S_3 , and S_3^- . Therefore, taking \mathbf{K} into account,

- a quantifier S is selected in $\{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$ to generate a new fuzzy formal context (X, Y_J, I_S) by merging the information related to (Z, W, J) and r (first step of the FRCA process);
- using the method introduced in [33], fuzzy concepts are extracted from (Z, W, J) and $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I_S)$, in order to obtain the information hidden in \mathbf{K} , where the fuzzy formal context $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I_S)$ is built by joining (X, Y, I) and (X, Y_J, I_S) : the attributes of Y_J are added to those of Y together with I_S , which is applied to the pairs of $X \times Y_J$ (second step of the FRCA process).

Certainly, the selection of the quantifier is crucial in the FRCA procedure since it affects the final concept classification: diverse fuzzy concepts arise from varying quantifiers. Indeed, let $S, S^* \in \{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$ such that $S \neq S^*$, the fuzzy formal contexts (X, Y_J, I_S) and (X, Y_J, I_{S^*}) do not coincide, and so, they correspond to two diverse families of fuzzy concepts. Hence, it could be useful to understand which quantifier to choose during the first step of the FRCA procedure, according to the final result that we are interested in. Such aspect motivates our findings, which are synthesized as follows. We discover the logical relations between the quantifiers of $\{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$ to arrange them in a graded version of the Aristotelian square. Accordingly, for each fuzzy relational context family, we construct a square of opposition having the fuzzy formal contexts (X, Y_J, I_{S_1}) , $(X, Y_J, I_{S_1^-})$, (X, Y_J, I_{S_3}) , and $(X, Y_J, I_{S_3^-})$ as vertices, considering that (X, Y, I_S) is defined utilizing S . Moreover, we examine the connections involving the pairs of operators (F_{I_S}, G_{I_S}) and $(F_{I_{S^*}}, G_{I_{S^*}})$. As a consequence, we find the existence of relations among fuzzy concepts produced by distinct quantifiers in $\{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$.

Let us present the organization of the rest of the article. Section 2 reviews the notions of Łukasiewicz algebra, universal and existential fuzzy quantifiers, and graded Aristotle’s square. Section 3 provides an overview of the main definitions and results concerning FFCA and FRCA. In Section 4, FRCA quantifiers and the corresponding fuzzy formal contexts are organized to form a square of opposition. Section 5 is devoted to analyzing the relations among the FFCA operators and their related fuzzy concepts, which are derived from different FRCA quantifiers. The last section finally presents concluding comments and addresses the possible future advancements stemming from our results.

Our results provide a twofold contribution to the advancement of Aristotle’s square. Indeed, they reveal a novel interpretation of the square of opposition within the framework of Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis, emphasizing its potential as a valuable tool for the analysis of data.

This work can be considered a follow-up and an extension of [50]: we give the full proofs of corollaries showing the logical relations between the universal and existential quantifiers, we organize such quantifiers in an Aristotelian square, we provide additional explanations and insights, and we investigate the consequences of the considered logical relations by taking into account FFCA operators that are diverse from those examined in [50].

Other FFCA approaches [51,52] are diverse to that considered in this article because they provide additional information about the membership degrees of the intents and are based on operators forming fuzzy Galois connections [53]. On the other hand, they produce a considerable number of fuzzy concepts, many of which are very similar to each other, so examining the final classification could be hard. So, in the future perspective to apply our results in data analysis, we have chosen to develop our study starting from the method given in [33].

2. Mathematical tools for fuzzy logic

By a *fuzzy set* A of a universe X , we mean a function $A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, where let $x \in X$, $A(x)$ is the truth degree of the statement “ x belongs to A ”.

We use the symbol $[0, 1]^X$ to denote the collection of all the fuzzy sets of X . Also, $A = \emptyset$ indicates that the equality $A(x) = 0$ holds for each $x \in X$.

As usual, if $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, we represent $A \in [0, 1]^X$ as follows:

$$A = \{a_1/x_1, \dots, a_n/x_n\}, \quad (1)$$

where $a_i = A(x_i)$. Furthermore, in (1), we omit a_i/x_i when $a_i = 0$, and we write x_i (instead of a_i/x_i) when $a_i = 1$.

Remark 1. A classical subset A of X can be viewed as a fuzzy set in $[0, 1]^X$ such that let $x \in A$,

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In this article, we choose the Łukasiewicz algebra as the structure of truth degrees.

Definition 1. The Łukasiewicz algebra (also known as *standard MV-algebra*) is an algebraic structure

$$\langle [0, 1], \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1 \rangle,$$

where

- (i) $a \wedge b = \min\{a, b\}$ (weak conjunction),
- (ii) $a \vee b = \max\{a, b\}$ (weak disjunction),
- (iii) $a \otimes b = \max\{0, a + b - 1\}$ (strong conjunction),
- (iv) $a \rightarrow b = \min\{1, 1 - a + b\}$ (implication),

for each $a, b \in [0, 1]$.

Additionally, derived operations are considered: for each $a, b \in [0, 1]$,

- (v) $\neg a = 1 - a$ (negation),
- (vi) $a \oplus b = \min\{1, a + b\}$ (strong disjunction).

The following theorem lists some important properties holding in the Łukasiewicz algebra.

Theorem 1. Let $\langle [0, 1], \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, 0, 1 \rangle$ be the Łukasiewicz algebra, then the following properties hold, for all $a, b, c, a_i, b_i \in [0, 1]$ with $i \in I = \{1, \dots, n\}$:

- (a) $\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i = 1$ if and only if $a_j = 1$, for each $j \in I$;
- (b) $\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i \leq a_j$, for each $j \in I$;
- (c) if $a_i \leq b_i$ for each $i \in I$, then $\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i \leq \bigvee_{i \in I} b_i$;
- (d) $\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i = 0$ if and only if $a_j = 0$, for each $j \in I$;
- (e) $\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i = 1$ if and only if there exists $j \in I$ such that $a_j = 1$;
- (f) $\bigotimes_{i \in I} a_i = 1$ if and only if $a_j = 1$, for each $j \in I$;
- (g) if $a = b$, then $\neg a = \neg b$;
- (h) $\neg \neg a = a$;
- (i) if $a \leq b$, then $a \oplus c \leq b \oplus c$;
- (j) $a \otimes b = b \otimes a$ and $a \oplus b = b \oplus a$;
- (k) $a \otimes \neg a = 0$;
- (l) if $a \leq b$ and $c \leq d$, then $a \otimes c \leq b \otimes d$;
- (m) $\bigvee_{i \in I} (a \otimes b_i) = a \otimes \bigvee_{i \in I} b_i$;
- (n) $\bigvee_{i \in I} (a_i \otimes a_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} a_i \otimes \bigvee_{i \in I} a_i$;
- (o) $a \otimes b \leq c$ if and only if $a \leq b \rightarrow c$ ¹;
- (p) $\neg(a \otimes b) = \neg a \oplus \neg b$;

¹ This is called *adjunction property* and holds in every residuated lattice.

- (q) $\neg(a \rightarrow b) = a \otimes \neg b$;
- (r) $a \rightarrow b = \neg a \oplus b$;
- (s) $a \rightarrow b = 1$ if and only if $a \leq b$.

2.1. Universal and existential quantifiers

In this subsection, we recall the definition of the universal and existential quantifiers given in [50].

Definition 2. The *positive universal quantifier* is a function

$$S_1 : [0, 1]^X \times [0, 1]^X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$S_1(A, B) = \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x), \quad \text{for each } A, B \in [0, 1]^X$$

Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$, $S_1(A, B)$ is the truth degree of the statement:

“all elements of A belong to B and there exists at least one element in A ”.

Example 1. We consider the fuzzy sets A and B of $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_{10}\}$ defined as follows:

$$A = \{x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.5/x_3, x_4, 0.9/x_5, 0.3/x_6, 0.7/x_7, 0.5/x_8, 0.4/x_9, x_{10}\};$$

$$B = \{0.8/x_1, 0.7/x_2, 0.4/x_3, 0.8/x_4, 0.5/x_5, 0.6/x_6, 0.5/x_7, x_8, 0.9/x_9, x_{10}\}.$$

We suppose that x_1, \dots, x_{10} are the students of a class and let $x \in X$, $A(x)$ and $B(x)$ are respectively the truth degrees to which

“the student x is good at calculations” and “the student x is good at problem-solving”.

According to Definition 2, we can easily find the value that S_1 assumes on A and B :

$$S_1(A, B) = ((1 \rightarrow 0.8) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 0.7) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 0.4) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 0.8) \wedge (0.9 \rightarrow 0.5) \wedge$$

$$(0.3 \rightarrow 0.6) \wedge (0.7 \rightarrow 0.5) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (0.4 \rightarrow 0.9) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 1)) \otimes (1 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.5 \vee 1$$

$$\vee 0.9 \vee 0.3 \vee 0.7 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.4 \vee 1) = (0.8 \wedge 1 \wedge 0.9 \wedge 0.8 \wedge 0.6 \wedge 1 \wedge 0.8 \wedge 1 \wedge 1 \wedge 1) \otimes 1 = 0.6 \otimes 1 = 0.6.$$

Therefore, $S_1(A, B) = 0.6$ is the truth degree to which

“at least one student is good at calculations and all students who are good at calculations are also good at problem-solving”.

Definition 3. The *negative universal quantifier* is a function

$$S_1^- : [0, 1]^X \times [0, 1]^X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$S_1^-(A, B) = \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x), \quad \text{for each } A, B \in [0, 1]^X.$$

Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$, $S_1^-(A, B)$ is the truth degree of the statement:

“all elements of A do not belong to B and there exists at least one element in A ”.

Example 2. Let A and B be the fuzzy sets of $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ defined in Example 1. By Definition 3, $S_1^-(A, B)$ is computed as follows:

$$S_1^-(A, B) = ((1 \rightarrow 0.2) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 0.3) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 0.6) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 0.2) \wedge (0.9 \rightarrow 0.5) \wedge$$

$$(0.3 \rightarrow 0.4) \wedge (0.7 \rightarrow 0.5) \wedge (0.5 \rightarrow 0) \wedge (0.4 \rightarrow 0.1) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 0)) \otimes (1 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.5 \vee 1$$

$$\vee 0.9 \vee 0.3 \vee 0.7 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.4 \vee 1) = (0.2 \wedge 0.8 \wedge 1 \wedge 0.2 \wedge 0.6 \wedge 1 \wedge 0.8 \wedge 0.5 \wedge 1 \wedge 0) \otimes 1 = 0 \otimes 1 = 0.$$

Therefore, $S_1^-(A, B) = 0$ is the truth degree to which

“at least one student is good at calculations and all students who are good at calculations are not good at problem-solving”.

Definition 4. The *positive existential quantifier* is a function

$$S_{\exists} : [0, 1]^X \times [0, 1]^X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$S_{\exists}(A, B) = \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes B(x)), \quad \text{for each } A, B \in [0, 1]^X.$$

Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$, $S_{\exists}(A, B)$ is the truth degree of the statement:

“if there exists at least one element in A , then there exists at least one element in both A and B ”.

Example 3. Let A and B be the fuzzy sets of $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ defined in Example 1. By Definition 4, $S_{\exists}(A, B)$ is computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\exists}(A, B) &= (1 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.5 \vee 1 \vee 0.9 \vee 0.3 \vee 0.7 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.4 \vee 1) \rightarrow ((1 \otimes 0.8) \vee (0.5 \otimes 0.7) \vee \\ &\quad (0.5 \otimes 0.4) \vee (1 \otimes 0.8) \vee (0.9 \otimes 0.5) \vee (0.3 \otimes 0.6) \vee (0.7 \otimes 0.5) \vee (0.5 \otimes 1) \vee (0.4 \otimes 0.9) \vee (1 \otimes 1)) = \\ &= 1 \rightarrow (0.8 \vee 0.2 \vee 0 \vee 0.8 \vee 0.4 \otimes 0 \vee 0.2 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.3 \vee 1) = 1 \rightarrow 1 = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $S_{\exists}(A, B)$ is the truth degree of the statement

“when at least a student of the class is good at calculations, at least one student is good at both calculations and problem-solving”.

Definition 5. The *negative existential quantifier* is a function

$$S_{\exists}^- : [0, 1]^X \times [0, 1]^X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$S_{\exists}^-(A, B) = \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes \neg B(x)), \quad \text{for each } A, B \in [0, 1]^X.$$

Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$, $S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$ is the truth degree of the statement:

“if there exists at least one element in A , then there exists at least one element in A that does not belong to B ”.

Example 4. Let A and B be the fuzzy sets of $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ defined in Example 1. By Definition 5, $S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$ is computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\exists}^-(A, B) &= (1 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.5 \vee 1 \vee 0.9 \vee 0.3 \vee 0.7 \vee 0.5 \vee 0.4 \vee 1) \rightarrow ((1 \otimes 0.2) \vee (0.5 \otimes 0.3) \vee \\ &\quad (0.5 \otimes 0.6) \vee (1 \otimes 0.2) \vee (0.9 \otimes 0.5) \vee (0.3 \otimes 0.4) \vee (0.7 \otimes 0.5) \vee (0.5 \otimes 0) \vee (0.4 \otimes 0.1) \vee (1 \otimes 0)) \\ &= 1 \rightarrow (0.2 \vee 0 \vee 0.1 \vee 0.2 \vee 0.4 \vee 0 \vee 0.2 \vee 0 \vee 0.4 \vee 0) = 1 \rightarrow 0.4 = 0.4. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $S_{\exists}^-(A, B) = 0.4$ is the truth degree to which

“when at least one student of the class is good at calculations, at least one of them is not good at problem-solving”.

Remark 2. The definition of $S_1(A, B)$, $S_1^-(A, B)$, $S_{\exists}(A, B)$, and $S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$ includes the sub-formula $\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x)$, which is called *existential import* (or *presupposition*) and corresponds to the assumption that the universe of quantification must be non-empty.

Let $S \in \{S_1, S_1^-, S_{\exists}, S_{\exists}^-\}$, when both A and B are classical subset of X , the formula of $S(A, B)$ can be rewritten as shown by the following theorems.

Theorem 2. Let $A, B \subseteq X$, then

$$(a) \quad S_1(A, B) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A \subseteq B \text{ and } A \neq \emptyset; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$(b) S_1^-(A, B) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A \subseteq X \setminus B \text{ and } A \neq \emptyset; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. (a) See Theorem 4.3 in [43].

(b) First of all, it is trivial that $S_1^-(A, B) \in \{0, 1\}$, when $A, B \subseteq X$.

Thus, let us prove that $S_1^-(A, B) = 1$ if and only if $A \subseteq X \setminus B$ and $A \neq \emptyset$.

By Definition 3 and by Theorem 1 (f), $S_1^-(A, B) = 1$ if and only if

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x) = 1 \text{ and } \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) = 1.$$

Moreover, by Theorem 1 ((a) and (e)), the latter equations respectively mean that

$$“A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x) = 1 \text{ for each } x \in X” \text{ and } “\text{there exists } \bar{x} \in X \text{ such that } A(\bar{x}) = 1”.$$

Finally,

- by Remark 1 and by Theorem 1 (s), “ $A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x) = 1$ for each $x \in X$ ” if and only if $A \subseteq X \setminus B$;
- by Remark 1, “there exists $\bar{x} \in X$ such that $A(\bar{x}) = 1$ ” if and only if $A \neq \emptyset$. \square

Theorem 3. Let $A, B \subseteq X$ such that $A \neq \emptyset$, then

$$(a) S_{\exists}(A, B) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A \cap B \neq \emptyset; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$(b) S_{\exists}^-(A, B) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A \cap (X \setminus B) \neq \emptyset; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. (a) See Theorem 4.2 in [43].

(b) Trivially, $S_{\exists}^-(A, B) \in \{0, 1\}$, when $A, B \subseteq X$.

Thus, let us prove that $S_{\exists}^-(A, B) = 1$ if and only if $A \cap (X \setminus B) \neq \emptyset$.

By hypothesis, $A \neq \emptyset$. Hence, using Remark 1, there exists $\bar{x} \in X$ such that $A(\bar{x}) = 1$. This means that

$$\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) = 1 \tag{2}$$

from Theorem 1 (e).

By Definition 5 and by Theorem 1 (s), $S_{\exists}^-(A, B) = 1$ if and only if $\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \leq \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x)$. Therefore, by (2), we are sure that $\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x) = 1$. Ultimately, by Remark 1 and by Theorem 1 ((e) and (f)), there exists $\bar{x} \in X$ such that $A(\bar{x}) = \neg B(\bar{x}) = 1$. Thus, by Remark 1, $A \cap (X \setminus B) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Remark 3. Let us underline that confining to classical sets, S_1 and S_{\exists} respectively coincide with the so-called *universal and existential scaling quantifiers* already defined in [54].

2.2. Graded square of opposition

In this article, a graded square of opposition exhibits the link between predicates interpreted by fuzzy relations.

By a *fuzzy relation* R between two universes X and Y , we mean a function $R : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$. Namely, R is a fuzzy set of the Cartesian product $X \times Y$. Thus, we indicate the collection of all fuzzy relations between X and Y with the symbol $[0, 1]^{X \times Y}$.

Remark 4. A fuzzy relation $R : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ where $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$ can be practically represented by Table 1, where the box corresponding to x_i and y_j displays the value $R(x_i, y_j) \in [0, 1]$.

In a graded square of opposition, we can distinguish four types of relations between predicates, which are called *relations of opposition* or *logical relations*:

Definition 6. Let P_A and P_B be the predicates interpreted by $A \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$ and $B \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$, respectively.²

P_A and P_B are *contraries* if and only if $A(x, y) \otimes B(x, y) = 0$, for all $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$;

² Recall that $\otimes, \oplus, \rightarrow$, and \neg are operations of the Łukasiewicz algebra.

Table 1
Fuzzy relation $R : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

R	y_1	...	y_j	...	y_m
x_1	$R(x_1, y_1)$...	$R(x_1, y_j)$...	$R(x_1, y_m)$
\vdots	\vdots		\vdots		\vdots
x_j	$R(x_j, y_1)$...	$R(x_j, y_j)$...	$R(x_j, y_m)$
\vdots	\vdots		\vdots		\vdots
x_n	$R(x_n, y_1)$...	$R(x_n, y_j)$...	$R(x_n, y_m)$

Fig. 2. The graded square of opposition with $A, E, I, O \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$.

Table 2
Fuzzy relations $A, E, I, O \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$.

A	y_1	y_2	E	y_1	y_2	I	y_1	y_2	O	y_1	y_2
x_1	0	0.5	x_1	0.3	0.2	x_1	0.7	0.8	x_1	1	0.5
x_2	0.7	0	x_2	0.3	0.6	x_2	0.7	0.4	x_2	0.3	1

P_A and P_B are *sub-contraries* if and only if $A(x, y) \oplus B(x, y) = 1$, for all $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$;

P_B is *sub-altern* of P_A if and only if $A(x, y) \rightarrow B(x, y) = 1$, for all $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$;

P_A and P_B are *contradictories* if and only if $A(x, y) = \neg B(x, y)$, for all $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$.

Definition 7. The fuzzy relations $A, E, I, O \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$ interpreting the predicates P_A, P_E, P_I , and P_O form a *graded square of opposition* if and only if

- P_A and P_E are contraries;
- P_I and P_O are sub-contraries;
- P_I is subaltern of P_A and P_O is subaltern of P_E ;
- P_A and P_O are contradictories, as well as P_E and P_I .

The graded square of opposition of Definition 7 is depicted by Fig. 2.

Example 5. We consider the fuzzy relations $A, E, I, O \in [0, 1]^{X \times Y}$ defined by Table 2, where $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$. Then, it is easy to verify that A, E, I , and O form a graded square of opposition:

- P_A and P_E are contraries: $A(x_i, y_j) \otimes E(x_i, y_j) = 0$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $A(x_1, y_1) \otimes E(x_1, y_1) = 0 \otimes 0.3 = 0$.
- P_I and P_O are sub-contraries: $I(x_i, y_j) \oplus O(x_i, y_j) = 1$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $I(x_2, y_1) \oplus O(x_2, y_1) = 0.7 \oplus 0.3 = 1$.
- P_I is subaltern of P_A : $A(x_i, y_j) \rightarrow I(x_i, y_j) = 1$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $A(x_1, y_2) \rightarrow I(x_1, y_2) = 0.5 \rightarrow 0.8$. Similarly, P_O is subaltern of P_E : $E(x_i, y_j) \rightarrow O(x_i, y_j) = 1$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $E(x_2, y_1) \rightarrow O(x_2, y_1) = 0.3 \rightarrow 0.3 = 1$.
- P_A and P_O are contradictories: $A(x_i, y_j) = \neg O(x_i, y_j)$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $A(x_2, y_2) = 0$, which is equal to $\neg O(x_2, y_2) = 1 - 1 = 0$. Similarly, P_E and P_I are contradictories: $E(x_i, y_j) = \neg I(x_i, y_j)$ for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. For example, $E(x_2, y_2) = 0.6$, which is equal to $\neg I(x_2, y_2) = 1 - 0.4 = 0.6$.

Consequently, for all $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$, we can graphically organize the values $A(x_i, y_j), E(x_i, y_j), I(x_i, y_j)$, and $O(x_i, y_j)$ in graded squares of opposition as shown by Figs. 3, 4, 5, and 6.

Fig. 3. The graded square of opposition with $A(x_1, y_1)$, $E(x_1, y_1)$, $I(x_1, y_1)$, and $O(x_1, y_1)$.

Fig. 4. The graded square of opposition with $A(x_2, y_1)$, $E(x_2, y_1)$, $I(x_2, y_1)$, and $O(x_2, y_1)$.

Fig. 5. The graded square of opposition with $A(x_1, y_2)$, $E(x_1, y_2)$, $I(x_1, y_2)$, and $O(x_1, y_2)$.

Fig. 6. The graded square of opposition with $A(x_2, y_2)$, $E(x_2, y_2)$, $I(x_2, y_2)$, and $O(x_2, y_2)$.

Table 3
The fuzzy formal context (X, Y, I) .

I	y_1	y_2	y_3
x_1	0.5	0.4	1
x_2	0.2	0.5	0.6
x_3	0.8	0.5	0.4

3. Fuzzy relational concept analysis

3.1. Fuzzy formal concept analysis

We deal with a fuzzy formal context (X, Y, I) , where X is a set of objects, Y is a set of attributes, and I is a fuzzy relation between objects and attributes, i.e. $I : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Remark 5. Obviously, a fuzzy formal context (X, Y, I) is univocally identified with its fuzzy relation $I : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$. Hence, according to Remark 4, (X, Y, I) is usually represented as a table.

A way to extract information from a fuzzy formal context (X, Y, I) consists of using the pair operators (F_I, G_I) and the mapping φ_I , which are defined as follows.

Definition 8. Let $T \in [0, 1]$, we consider the operators $F_I : 2^X \rightarrow 2^Y$ and $G_I : 2^Y \rightarrow 2^X$ such that

$$F_I(A) = \{y \in Y \mid I(x, y) \geq T \text{ for each } x \in A\}, \text{ for each } A \subseteq X;$$

$$G_I(B) = \{x \in X \mid I(x, y) \geq T \text{ for each } y \in B\}, \text{ for each } B \subseteq Y.$$

Example 6. Let (X, Y, I) be the fuzzy formal context defined by Table 3.

According to Definition 8, if $T = 0.4$, then $F_I(\{x_2, x_3\}) = \{y_2, y_3\}$ and $G_I(\{y_1, y_2\}) = \{x_1, x_3\}$.

Definition 9. Let (X, Y, I) be a fuzzy formal context, we consider the mapping $\varphi_I : 2^X \rightarrow [0, 1]^X$ such that

$$\varphi_I(A)(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \notin A; \\ \min_{y \in F_I(A)} I(x, y) & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

for each $A \subseteq X$ (when $F_I(A) = \emptyset$, we set $\varphi_I(A) = \emptyset$).

By (3), we can immediately understand that $\varphi_I(A)$ is a fuzzy set of X depending on both $T \in [0, 1]$ and (X, Y, I) .

Example 7. Let us focus on Example 6. If $A = \{x_2, x_3\}$, then $\varphi_I(A)$ is the fuzzy set of $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_I(A)(x_1) = 0, \varphi_I(A)(x_2) = \min\{I(x_2, y_2), I(x_2, y_3)\} = \min\{0.5, 0.6\} = 0.5, \\ \text{and } \varphi_I(A)(x_3) = \min\{I(x_3, y_2), I(x_3, y_3)\} = \min\{0.5, 0.4\} = 0.4. \end{aligned}$$

In the sequel, we need the following proposition.³

Proposition 1. Let (X, Y, I) and (X, Y, I^*) be fuzzy formal contexts and let $T > 0$. If $A, A' \subseteq X$ such that $\varphi_I(A) = \varphi_{I^*}(A')$, then $A = A'$.

Proof. Let $A, A' \subseteq X$ such that $\varphi_I(A) = \varphi_{I^*}(A')$, we first intend to prove that $A \subseteq A'$.

Let $x \in A$, then $\varphi_I(A)(x) = \min_{y \in F_I(A)} I(x, y)$ from (3). Moreover, $I(x, y) \geq T$ for each $y \in F_I(A)$ from Definition 8 and $T > 0$ from hypothesis. Consequently, $\varphi_I(A)(x) > 0$.

Since we have supposed that $\varphi_I(A) = \varphi_{I^*}(A')$, the inequality $\varphi_{I^*}(A')(x) > 0$ holds too. As a consequence, by (3), it must be true that $x \in A'$.

Symmetrically, we can prove that $A' \subseteq A$. \square

In the following definition, the notion of fuzzy concept is given.

Definition 10. Let $T > 0$ and let (X, Y, I) be a fuzzy formal context, a *fuzzy concept* is a pair $(\varphi_I(A), B)$, where $F_I(A) = B$ and $G_I(B) = A$.

$\varphi_I(A)$ and B are respectively called the *extent* and *intent* of the related fuzzy concept.

According to Definition 10, if $(\varphi_I(A), B)$ is a fuzzy concept, then “ A is the set of all objects of X having all attributes in B (with a degree of at least T)”, and dually, “ B is the set of all attributes of Y shared by all objects of A (with a degree of at least T)”. Moreover, let $x \in X$, $\varphi_I(A)(x)$ is the truth degree to which “ x has all attributes of B (with a degree of at least T)”.

We use the symbol $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y, I)$ to denote the collection of all fuzzy formal contexts that can be defined starting from (X, Y, I) and $T \in (0, 1]$.

Example 8. Let us consider Example 6, then

$$\mathcal{B}_{0.4}(X, Y, I) = \{(\varphi_I(X), \{y_2, y_3\}), (\varphi_I(\{x_1, x_3\}), Y)\},$$

where

$$\varphi_I(X) = \{0.4/x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.4/x_3\} \text{ and } \varphi_I(\{x_1, x_3\}) = \{0.4/x_1, 0.4/x_3\}.$$

To understand the meaning of the fuzzy concepts of $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y, I)$, we suppose that the objects x_1, x_2 , and x_3 represent the students *Alice*, *Bob*, and *Carol*, and the attributes y_1, y_2 , and y_3 represent the skills *oral communication*, *calculations*, and *problem-solving*, respectively. Then, $(\varphi_I(X), \{y_1, y_2\})$ and $(\varphi_I(\{x_1, x_3\}), Y)$ reveal the following information:

- All three students are good at both oral communication and calculations (Alice and Carol with a degree of at least 0.4, while Bob with a degree of at least 0.5).
- Oral communication and problem-solving are all skills that are shared by all three students (with a degree of at least 0.4).
- Alice and Carol are all students who have all skills (both with a degree of at least 0.4).

Remark 6. The operators F_I and G_I acting on a crisp relation I on $X \times Y$, namely

$$I(x, y) \in \{0, 1\}, \text{ for each } x \in X \text{ and for each } y \in Y,$$

coincide with the standard FCA operators:

$$F_I(A) = \{y \in Y \mid I(x, y) = 1 \text{ for each } x \in A\} \text{ for each } A \subseteq X;$$

³ Both φ_I and φ_{I^*} are considered by fixing the same threshold T .

$$G_I(B) = \{x \in X \mid I(x, y) = 1 \text{ for each } y \in B\}, \text{ for each } B \subseteq Y.$$

Then, for each $T \in (0, 1]$, $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y, I)$ is the collection of the standard formal concepts extracted from (X, Y, I) : let $A \subseteq X$ and let $B \subseteq Y$,

$$(A, B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y, I) \text{ if and only if } F_I(A) = B \text{ and } G_I(B) = A.$$

3.2. Extracting concepts from fuzzy relational context families

This subsection describes the FRCA procedure, which was introduced for mining fuzzy concepts from fuzzy multi-relational datasets ⁴ [43]. It involves the choice of one of the definitions for fuzzy concepts existing in the literature, and here, we take into account that given by Definition 10.

For convenience, we confine to the simplest fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) , where

- \mathbf{K} is made of two fuzzy formal contexts (X, Y, I) and (Z, W, J) , and
- \mathbf{R} is made of a fuzzy relation $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

In more complex fuzzy relational context families, we get $|\mathbf{K}| > 2$ and $|\mathbf{R}| > 1$. Let $x \in X$, we use the symbol r^x to denote the fuzzy set of Z such that

$$r^x(z) = r(x, z), \text{ for each } z \in Z.$$

The input of the FRCA procedure is (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) and the output is obtained in three fundamental steps.

1. The collection of fuzzy concepts $\mathcal{B}_T(Z, W, J)$ is generated.
2. A new fuzzy formal context $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$ is constructed by uniting (X, Y, I) and the new fuzzy formal context (X, Y_J, I^*) .
Let us specify how Y_J and I^* are defined.
 Y_J is a new set of attributes called *relational attributes*:

$$Y_J = \{y_C \mid C \in \mathcal{B}_T(Z, W, J)\}. \quad (4)$$

I^* is a new fuzzy relation between X and Y_J :

$$I^*(x, y_C) = S(r^x, E_C), \text{ for all } x \in X \text{ and } y_C \in Y_J, \quad (5)$$

where $S \in \{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$ and E_C is the extent (namely, the first component) of the concept C of $\mathcal{B}_T(Z, W, J)$.

Let $C \in \mathcal{B}_T(Z, W, J)$, the meaning of y_C and I^* strictly depend on the choice of the fuzzy quantifier $S \in \{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$. Hence, by (5), considering that

let $z \in Z$, $E_C(z)$ is the truth degree to which “ z has all attributes in C ”,

if $S = S_1$, then $I^*(x, y_C)$ is the truth degree to which “all objects of Z that are in relation with x (w.r.t. r) have all attributes in C ”;

if $S = S_1^-$, then $I^*(x, y_C)$ is the truth degree to which “all objects of Z that are in relation with x (w.r.t. r) do not have any attributes in C ”;

if $S = S_3$, then $I^*(x, y_C)$ is the truth degree to which “at least one element of Z that is in relation with x (w.r.t. r) has all attributes in C ”;

$S = S_3^-$, then $I^*(x, y_C)$ is the truth degree to which “at least one element of Z that is in relation with x (w.r.t. r) does not have all attributes in C ”.⁵

Therefore, the fuzzy relation $I \cup I^*$ is defined as follows:

$$(I \cup I^*)(x, y) = \begin{cases} I(x, y) & \text{if } y \in Y; \\ I^*(x, y) & \text{if } y = y_C. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

One of the quantifiers among S_1 , S_1^- , S_3 , and S_3^- is selected to define I^* based on the information you want to extract from (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) .

3. A collection of fuzzy concepts $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$ is extracted from $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$.

Thus, by following the previous steps, we can find the fuzzy concepts of $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$ and $\mathcal{B}_T(Z, W, J)$, which are the final result generated by the FRCA procedure.

⁴ Recall that FRCA is the abbreviation of Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis.

⁵ According to the definition of S_1 , S_1^- , S_3 , and S_3^- such sentences should include the existential import, which is omitted so as not to make reading difficult.

Table 4
The fuzzy formal context (Z, W, J) and the fuzzy relation $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

J	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	r	z_1	z_2	z_3
z_1	0	1	0.5	0	x_1	0.5	0	1
z_2	0.3	0	0.8	1	x_2	0.8	0.3	0.7
z_3	0	0.6	0.2	0.9	x_3	0.6	0.2	0

Table 5
The fuzzy formal context $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$.

$I \cup I^*$	y_1	y_2	y_3	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}	y_{C_7}	y_{C_8}
x_1	0.5	0.4	1	1	0	0.6	0.5	0	0	0.5	0
x_2	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.1	0.5	0	0.1	0	0	0
x_3	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0	0.4	0	0	0

The following is an illustrative example.

Example 9. We consider the fuzzy relational context family

$$(\mathbf{K} = \{(X, Y, I), (Z, W, J)\}, \mathbf{R} = \{r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]\}),$$

where (X, Y, I) , (Z, W, J) , and $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined by Tables 3 and 4.

We assume that the objects of X and Z are students, the attributes of Y and W are skills, and the relation r expresses how much the students of X and Z are similar concerning the results that they achieved in several tests. In particular, as shown by Example 8, x_1, x_2 , and x_3 indicate the students *Alice*, *Bob*, and *Carol*, and y_1, y_2 , and y_3 indicate the skills *Oral communication*, *Calculations*, and *Problem-solving*. Additionally, we suppose that z_1, z_2 , and z_3 are the students *Daniel*, *Emily*, and *Francis*, and w_1, w_2, w_3 , and w_4 are the skills *Time management*, *Creativity*, *Critical thinking*, and *Collaboration*.

In the sequel, we follow the steps of the FRCA procedure described above. But first, we would like to anticipate that the final result in terms of fuzzy concepts highlights the relationship between the students of X and the skills of W , although it is not explicit in (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) .

1. We consider the fuzzy concepts derived from (Z, W, J) and $T = 0.4$ by using Definition 10:

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= (\{z_1, z_2, z_3\}, \emptyset); \\ C_2 &= (\{0.5/z_1, 0.8/z_2\}, \{w_3\}); \\ C_3 &= (\{z_1, 0.6/z_3\}, \{w_2\}); \\ C_4 &= (\{z_2, 0.9/z_3\}, \{w_4\}); \\ C_5 &= (\{0.5/z_1\}, \{w_2, w_3\}); \\ C_6 &= (\{0.8/z_2\}, \{w_3, w_4\}); \\ C_7 &= (\{0.6/z_3\}, \{w_2, w_4\}); \\ C_8 &= (\emptyset, \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}). \end{aligned}$$

2. We construct the new fuzzy formal context $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$.

- The set of all relational attributes is $Y_J = \{y_{C_1}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}$.
- To determine I^* , we choose the positive universal quantifier S_1 given by Definition 2. Thus, we need the fuzzy sets r^{x_1}, r^{x_2} , and r^{x_3} (observe that r^{x_i} is given by the row of x_i in Table 4) together with the extents of the fuzzy concepts C_1, \dots, C_8 (they are the first components of C_1, \dots, C_8).

Hence, by (5), $I^*(x_1, y_{C_1}) = S_1(r^{x_1}, E_{C_1}) = ((0.5 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (0 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 1)) \otimes (1 \vee 1 \vee 1) = 1 \otimes 1 = 1$, $I^*(x_1, y_{C_2}) = S_1(r^{x_1}, E_{C_2}) = ((0.5 \rightarrow 0.5) \wedge (0 \rightarrow 0.8) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 0)) \otimes (0.5 \vee 0.8 \vee 0) = 0 \otimes 0.8 = 0$, and so on. Therefore, the fuzzy relation $I \cup I^*$ is shown in Table 5.

Observe that the sub-table I^* connects the objects of X with the attributes of W using both J and r . For example, $I^*(x_2, y_{C_3})$ is the truth degree to which “*Bob achieved the same results as all students in Z who are good at critical thinking*”.

3. We consider the fuzzy concepts derived from $(X, Y \cup Y_J, I \cup I^*)$ and $T = 0.4$ by using Definition 10:

$$\begin{aligned} C'_1 &= (\{0.4/x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.4/x_3\}, \{y_2, y_3, y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}); \\ C'_2 &= (\{0.4/x_1, 0.4/x_3\}, \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}); \\ C'_3 &= (\{0.4/x_1\}, \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}, y_{C_7}\}); \\ C'_4 &= (\{0.4/x_3\}, \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}); \\ C'_5 &= (\emptyset, \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_{C_1}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the fuzzy concepts C_1, \dots, C_8 and C'_1, \dots, C'_5 are the granules of information extracted from (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) .

Remark 7. When $I : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $J : Z \times W \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are crisp relations, namely

$$I(x, y), J(z, w), r(x, z) \in \{0, 1\} \text{ for each } x \in X, y \in Y, z \in Z, \text{ and } w \in W,$$

(**K, R**) corresponds to the relational context family already defined in standard RCA [54]. Moreover, as explained in Remark 6, the concept-forming operators of Definition 8 coincide with the standard ones.

Thus, regardless of the choice of T in $(0, 1]$, the sets $B_T(X, Y \cup Y_J, I^*)$ and $B_T(Z, W, J)$ are made of classical formal concepts and coincide with the output of the standard RCA procedure described in [54]. In particular, by Remark 3,

- if I^* is derived from S_1 , the final concepts are those obtained by using the universal scaling quantifier given in [54],
- if I^* is derived from S_3 , the final concepts are those obtained by using the existential scaling quantifier given in [54].

The negative universal and existential quantifiers S_1^- and S_3^- can be traced back to the classical RCA method too. In fact, $S_1^-(r^x, E_C)$ and $S_3^-(r^x, E_C)$ can be obtained by applying the universal and existential scaling quantifiers to the sets r^x and $Z \setminus E_C$.

In this article, we confine our study to the sub-context (X, Y_J, I^*) , considering that it depends on the choice of one of the quantifiers in $\{S_1, S_1^-, S_3, S_3^-\}$. Therefore, we are interested in $B_T(X, Y_J, I^*)$.

4. Relations of opposition between fuzzy formal contexts

The principal result of this section is shown by Theorem 4, where a graded square of opposition is constructed by using the fuzzy formal contexts corresponding to the fuzzy quantifiers $S_1, S_1^-, S_3,$ and S_3^- defined in Subsection 2.1. To prove Theorem 4, we need a list of corollaries (Corollaries 1-6) deriving from Theorem 1 and describing the mathematical relationship between the fuzzy quantifiers $S_1, S_1^-, S_3,$ and S_3^- .

Corollary 1. $S_1(A, B) \otimes S_1^-(A, B) = 0$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$. By Lemma 1 (b),

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \leq A(\bar{x}) \rightarrow B(\bar{x}) \text{ and } \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \leq A(\bar{x}) \rightarrow \neg B(\bar{x}), \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

Then, by the adjunction property (see Theorem 1 (o)),

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \leq B(\bar{x}) \text{ and } \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \leq \neg B(\bar{x}), \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

As a consequence, using Theorem 1 ((l) and (j)), we have

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \leq B(\bar{x}) \otimes \neg B(\bar{x}), \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

By Theorem 1 (k), it is true that $B(\bar{x}) \otimes \neg B(\bar{x}) = 0$ for each $\bar{x} \in X$; hence,

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \otimes A(\bar{x}) = 0 \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

Moreover, due to Theorem 1 (d), we get

$$\bigvee_{x \in X} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes A(x) \otimes A(x) \right) = 0.$$

By Theorem 1 (m),

$$\left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \right) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = 0. \tag{7}$$

Considering that $\bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x)$ from Theorem 1 (n), the following equation holds:

$$\left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \right) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) = 0.$$

Finally, since \otimes is commutative (Theorem 1 (j)), we can deduce that

$$\left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \otimes \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = 0.$$

Namely, according to Definitions 2 and 3, it is true that $S_1(A, B) \otimes S_1^-(A, B) = 0$. \square

Corollary 2. $S_3(A, B) \oplus S_3^-(A, B) = 1$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$. We have previously proved that the following equality holds (see (7) in the proof of Corollary 1):

$$\left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \right) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = 0.$$

Therefore, using Theorem 1 (g) and considering that the equation $\neg 0 = 1$ is true in the Łukasiewicz algebra, we can write that

$$\neg \left(\left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \right) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) \right) = 1. \tag{8}$$

Furthermore, taking into account Theorem 1 (p) twice, we obtain

$$\neg \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \right) \oplus \neg \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = 1 \tag{9}$$

and

$$\neg \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \oplus \neg \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \oplus \neg \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = 1. \tag{10}$$

Now, let us recall that in the Łukasiewicz algebra, the equation $\neg(a \wedge b) = \neg a \vee \neg b$ is satisfied for all $a, b \in [0, 1]$; hence,

$$\bigvee_{x \in X} \neg(A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \oplus \bigvee_{x \in X} \neg(A(x) \rightarrow \neg B(x)) \oplus \neg \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) = 1. \tag{11}$$

By Theorem 1 ((q), (h), and (p)),

$$\bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes \neg B(x)) \oplus \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes B(x)) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = 1. \tag{12}$$

Since \oplus is commutative (see Theorem 1 (j)), we have

$$\left(\neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \oplus \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes B(x)) \right) \oplus \left(\neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \oplus \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes \neg B(x)) \right) = 1. \tag{13}$$

Ultimately, by Theorem 1 (r), we can conclude that

$$\left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes \neg B(x)) \right) \oplus \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes B(x)) \right) = 1. \tag{14}$$

Namely, according to Definition 4 and 5, it is true that $S_3(A, B) \oplus S_3^-(A, B) = 1$. \square

Corollary 3. $S_1(A, B) \leq S_3(A, B)$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$. Recall that in the proof of Corollary 1, we have shown that

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \leq B(\bar{x}), \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

Hence, by Theorem 1 (l),

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \otimes A(\bar{x}) \leq A(\bar{x}) \otimes B(\bar{x}), \text{ for each } \bar{x} \in X.$$

Employing Theorem 1 ((c) and (m)),

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \otimes A(x)) \leq \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes B(x).$$

Moreover, by Theorem 1 (n), we obtain that

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \leq \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes B(x).$$

Lastly, due to the adjunction property (see Theorem 1 (o)), we can conclude that

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \leq \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes B(x).$$

Namely, according to Definitions 2 and 4, it is true that $S_1(A, B) \leq S_{\exists}(A, B)$, \square

Corollary 4. $S_1^-(A, B) \leq S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. The proof can be easily obtained by exchanging $B(x)$ with $\neg B(x)$ in the proof of Corollary 3. \square

Corollary 5. $\neg S_1(A, B) = S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. Let $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$. By Theorem 1 (p), we can write

$$\neg \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = \neg \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} A(x) \rightarrow B(x) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right).$$

Moreover, in the Lukasiewicz algebra, the equation $\neg(a \wedge b) = \neg a \vee \neg b$ holds for each $a, b \in [0, 1]$; hence,

$$\neg \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} \neg(A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right).$$

By Theorem 1 (q),

$$\left(\bigvee_{x \in X} \neg(A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right).$$

Therefore, using Theorem 1 (j) and (r), we get

$$\left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x) \right) \oplus \neg \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \rightarrow \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x) \right).$$

Finally, considering the chain of equalities shown above, we get

$$\neg \left(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \rightarrow B(x)) \otimes \bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) = \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \right) \rightarrow \left(\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \otimes \neg B(x) \right).$$

Namely, according to Definitions 2 and 5, it is true that $\neg S_1(A, B) = S_{\exists}^-(A, B)$. \square

Corollary 6. $S_1^-(A, B) = \neg S_{\exists}(A, B)$, for all $A, B \in [0, 1]^X$.

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Corollary 5, and so, it is omitted. \square

In the sequel, we deal with the fuzzy relational context family

$$(\mathbf{K} = \{(X, Y, I), (Z, W, J)\}, \mathbf{R} = r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1])$$

described at the beginning of Subsection 3.2. In addition, we use the symbols (X, Y_J, I_1^+) , (X, Y_J, I_1^-) , (X, Y_J, I_3^+) , and (X, Y_J, I_3^-) to denote the fuzzy formal contexts, where Y_J is the set of relational attributes given by (4) and I_1^+ , I_1^- , I_3^+ , and I_3^- are the fuzzy relations on $X \times Y_J$ respectively obtained from S_1 , S_1^- , S_{\exists} , and S_{\exists}^- by (5).

The following theorem is the principal result of this section and shows all the logical relations involving the predicates interpreted by I_1^+ , I_1^- , I_3^+ , and I_3^- . Thus, it allows such fuzzy relations to be organized in a graded square of opposition.

Theorem 4. Let (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) be a fuzzy relational context family, then I_1^+ , I_1^- , I_3^+ , and I_3^- are the vertices of a graded square of opposition as represented by Fig. 7. Equivalently, the following relations of opposition are satisfied⁶:

- (a) $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ are contraries;
- (b) $P_{I_3^+}$ and $P_{I_3^-}$ are sub-contraries;
- (c) $P_{I_3^+}$ is sub-altern of $P_{I_1^+}$;
- (d) $P_{I_3^-}$ is sub-altern of $P_{I_1^-}$;

⁶ The symbol P_I denotes the predicate interpreted by I .

Fig. 7. The graded square of opposition with I_1^+, I_1^-, I_3^+ , and I_3^- .

Table 6

The fuzzy relation $I_1^+ : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.4$.

I_1^+	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}	y_{C_7}	y_{C_8}
x_1	1	0	0.6	0.5	0	0	0.5	0
x_2	0.8	0.1	0.5	0	0.1	0	0	0
x_3	0.6	0.5	0.4	0	0.4	0	0	0

Table 7

The fuzzy relation $I_1^- : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.4$.

I_1^-	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}	y_{C_7}	y_{C_8}
x_1	0	1	0.4	0.1	1	1	0.4	1
x_2	0	0.5	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.8
x_3	0	0.5	0	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6

Table 8

The fuzzy relation $I_3^+ : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.4$.

I_3^+	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}	y_{C_7}	y_{C_8}
x_1	1	0	0.6	0.9	0	0	0.6	0
x_2	1	0.5	1	0.8	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2
x_3	1	0.5	1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4

- (e) $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_3^-}$ are contradictories;
- (f) $P_{I_1^-}$ and $P_{I_3^+}$ are contradictories.

Proof. Let us prove item (a). Given $x \in X$ and $y \in Y_J$, we can observe that $I_1^+(x, y_C) = S_1(r^x, E_C)$ and $I_1^-(x, y_C) = S_1^-(r^x, E_C)$ from (5). Moreover, by Corollary 1, $S_1(r^x, E_C) \otimes S_1^-(r^x, E_C) = 0$. Consequently, $I_1^+(x, y) \otimes I_1^-(x, y) = 0$. This means that $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ are contraries from Definition 6.

The proof related to the remaining relations of opposition can be analogously obtained. It follows from (5), Definition 6, and Corollaries 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. \square

By Remark 5, the fuzzy relations I_1^+, I_1^-, I_3^+ , and I_3^- are respectively equivalent to the fuzzy formal contexts (X, Y_J, I_1^+) , (X, Y_J, I_1^-) , (X, Y_J, I_3^+) , and (X, Y_J, I_3^-) . Consequently, by Theorem 4, we can think of a model of the graded square of opposition, in terms of fuzzy formal contexts.

Example 10. We consider the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) defined in Example 9. Thus, (X, Y, I) , (Z, W, J) , and $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are given by Tables 3 and 4.

Let us recall that $Y_J = \{y_{C_1}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}$. Furthermore, using (5), it is easy to check that the fuzzy relations I_1^+, I_1^-, I_3^+ , and I_3^- are respectively represented by Tables 6, 7, 8, and 9.

Therefore, according to Theorem 4, these form a graded square of opposition as shown by Fig. 7. As a consequence, for each $x \in X$ and for each $y_C \in Y_J$, the mathematical relationships involving the values $I_1^+(x, y_C)$, $I_1^-(x, y_C)$, $I_3^+(x, y_C)$, and $I_3^-(x, y_C)$ can be graphically exhibited in a square too. Let us show a pair of examples.

We firstly focus on the values that I_1^+, I_1^-, I_3^+ , and I_3^- assume on x_2 and y_{C_1} . Hence, as schematized by Fig. 8, we get

$$I_1^+(x_2, y_{C_1}) \otimes I_1^-(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0.8 \otimes 0 = 0,$$

Table 9
The fuzzy relation $I_{\exists}^- : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.4$.

I_{\exists}^-	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}	y_{C_7}	y_{C_8}
x_1	0	1	0.4	0.5	1	1	0.5	1
x_2	0.2	0.9	0.5	1	0.9	1	1	1
x_3	0.4	0.5	0.6	1	0.6	1	1	1

Fig. 8. The graded square of opposition related to x_2 and y_{C_1} .

Fig. 9. The graded square of opposition related to x_3 and y_{C_5} .

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{\exists}^+(x_2, y_{C_1}) \oplus I_{\exists}^-(x_2, y_{C_1}) &= 1 \oplus 0.2 = 1, \\
 I_1^+(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0.8 &\text{ is less than } I_{\exists}^+(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 1, \\
 I_1^-(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0 &\text{ is less than } I_{\exists}^-(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0.2, \\
 I_1^+(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0.8 &= \neg 0.2 = \neg I_{\exists}^-(x_2, y_{C_1}), \text{ and} \\
 I_1^-(x_2, y_{C_1}) = 0 &= \neg 1 = \neg I_{\exists}^+(x_2, y_{C_1}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, taking into account x_3 and y_{C_5} , as schematized by Fig. 9, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1^+(x_3, y_{C_5}) \otimes I_1^-(x_3, y_{C_5}) &= 0.4 \otimes 0.5 = 0, \\
 I_{\exists}^+(x_3, y_{C_5}) \oplus I_{\exists}^-(x_3, y_{C_5}) &= 0.5 \oplus 0.6 = 1, \\
 I_1^+(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.4 &\text{ is less than } I_{\exists}^+(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.5, \\
 I_1^-(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.5 &\text{ is less than } I_{\exists}^-(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.6, \\
 I_1^+(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.4 &= \neg 0.6 = \neg I_{\exists}^-(x_3, y_{C_5}), \text{ and} \\
 I_1^-(x_3, y_{C_5}) = 0.5 &= \neg 0.5 = \neg I_{\exists}^+(x_3, y_{C_5}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 8. Let us rewrite the relations of opposition of Theorem 4, when (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) is made of crisp relations.

First of all, we can observe that I_1^+ , I_1^- , I_{\exists}^+ , and I_{\exists}^- are crisp relations too. Furthermore, by Remark 1, a crisp relation $I : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ can be viewed as a set of special pairs of $X \times Y$:

$$I = \{(x, y) \in X \times Y \mid I(x, y) = 1\}.$$

Hence, the logical relations of Theorem 4 can be expressed in terms of classical sets:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Contrary: } I_1^+ \cap I_1^- &= \emptyset; \\
 \text{Sub-contrary: } I_{\exists}^+ \cup I_{\exists}^- &= X \times Y_J; \\
 \text{Sub-alternation: } I_1^+ \subseteq I_{\exists}^+ &\text{ and } I_1^- \subseteq I_{\exists}^-; \\
 \text{Contradictory: } I_1^+ = (X \times Y_J) \setminus I_{\exists}^- &\text{ and } I_1^- = (X \times Y_J) \setminus I_{\exists}^+.
 \end{aligned}$$

5. Implications of the square of opposition in fuzzy relational concept analysis

This section highlights connections involving the pairs of concept-forming operators (F_I, G_I) and (F_{I^*}, G_{I^*}) given by Definition 8, where both I and I^* belong to $\{I_1^+, I_1^-, I_{\exists}^+, I_{\exists}^-\}$ and a certain relation of opposition holds between P_I and P_{I^*} as shown by Theorem 4. Moreover, let $T \in (0, 1]$, correspondences between the fuzzy concepts of $B_T(X, Y_J, I)$ and $B_T(X, Y_J, I^*)$ are established.⁷

⁷ As done so far, we take into account the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) introduced at the beginning of Subsection 3.2.

5.1. Implications of the relation of contrary

When choosing a particular threshold, the operators $F_{I_1^+}$ and $F_{I_1^-}$ transform a given non-empty set of objects into disjoint sets of attributes.

Theorem 5. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$, then $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A) = \emptyset$ for each $\emptyset \subset A \subseteq X$.

Proof. Let $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^+}(A)$, we intend to prove that $\bar{y} \notin F_{I_1^-}(A)$. By Definition 8, $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^+}(A)$ implies that $I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) \geq T$ for each $x \in A$. Thus, since $T > \frac{1}{2}$, we are sure that

$$I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) > \frac{1}{2}, \text{ for each } x \in A. \tag{15}$$

Moreover, by Theorem 4 (a), $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ are contraries. Namely, by Definition 6, $I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) \otimes I_1^-(x, \bar{y}) = 0$, for each $x \in A$. By Definition 1, for each $x \in A$,

$$I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) \otimes I_1^-(x, \bar{y}) = 0 \text{ if and only if } I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) + I_1^-(x, \bar{y}) \leq 1.$$

Therefore, the latter inequality together with (15) implies that $I_1^-(x, \bar{y}) < \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in A$. Hence, we deduce that $I_1^-(x, \bar{y}) < T$ for each $x \in A$. Using Definition 8 again, it must be true that $\bar{y} \notin F_{I_1^-}(A)$.

By exchanging the role of I_1^+ and I_1^- , we can symmetrically prove that “if $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^-}(A)$, then $\bar{y} \notin F_{I_1^+}(A)$ ”.

Lastly, we can conclude that $F_{I_1^+}(A)$ and $F_{I_1^-}(A)$ are disjoint. \square

When choosing a particular threshold, the operators $G_{I_1^+}$ and $G_{I_1^-}$ transform a given non-empty set of attributes into disjoint sets of objects.

Theorem 6. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$, then $G_{I_1^+}(B) \cap G_{I_1^-}(B) = \emptyset$ for each $\emptyset \subset B \subseteq Y_J$.

Proof. The thesis follows from the contrariety of $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ (see Theorem 4 (a)) and from Definition 8. The proof steps are analogous to those of the previous theorem, and so, they are omitted. \square

As a consequence of Theorems 5 and 6, we get that $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$ cannot have fuzzy concepts in common (except when one of their components is empty).

Corollary 7. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$,

$$\text{if } (\tilde{A}, B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+) \cap \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-), \text{ then } \tilde{A} = \emptyset \text{ or } B = \emptyset.^8$$

Proof. Let $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and let $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$.

- Suppose that $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A) = \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')$ with $A \neq \emptyset$ and $A' \neq \emptyset$, then $A = A'$ from Proposition 1. By Theorem 5, $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^+}(A') = \emptyset$. Thus, by Definition 8, $B \cap B' = \emptyset$. Then, $B = B'$ if and only if $B = B' = \emptyset$.
- Vice-versa, by Theorem 6, if B is a non-empty set of attributes equal to B' , then $G_{I_1^+}(B) \cap G_{I_1^-}(B') = \emptyset$. Consequently, by Definition 8, $A \cap A' = \emptyset$. Therefore, $A = A'$ if and only if $A = A' = \emptyset$. \square

Example 11. We consider the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) defined in Example 9 (thus, (X, Y, Z) , (Z, W, J) , and $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are represented by Tables 3 and 4, respectively). Here, we take into account $T = 0.6$, which satisfies the hypothesis of Theorems 5 and 6, and Corollary 7. Then, $\mathcal{B}_{0.6}(Z, W, J)$ is made of the following fuzzy concepts:

- $C_1 = (\{z_1, z_2, z_3\}, \emptyset)$;
- $C_2 = (\{z_1, 0.6/z_3\}, \{w_2\})$;
- $C_3 = (\{z_2, 0.9/z_3\}, \{w_4\})$;
- $C_4 = (\{0.8/z_2\}, \{w_3, w_4\})$;
- $C_5 = (\{0.6/z_3\}, \{w_2, w_4\})$;

⁸ By Definition 10, \tilde{A} is a fuzzy set of X .

Table 10
The fuzzy relation $I_1^+ : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.6$.

I_1^+	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}
x_1	1	0.6	0.5	0	0.5	0
x_2	0.8	0.5	0	0	0	0
x_3	0.6	0.4	0	0	0	0

Table 11
The fuzzy relation $I_1^- : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T = 0.6$.

I_1^-	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}
x_1	0	0.4	0.1	1	0.4	1
x_2	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.5	0.8
x_3	0	0	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.6

$$C_6 = (\emptyset, \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}).$$

Thus, I_1^+ and I_1^- are respectively defined by Tables 10 and 11.

Let $A = \{x_1, x_2\}$. If $T = 0.6$, then $F_{I_1^+}(A) = \{y_{C_1}\}$ and $F_{I_1^-}(A) = \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}\}$ from Definition 8. According to Theorem 5, we get

$$F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A) = \{y_{C_1}\} \cap \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}\} = \emptyset.$$

Moreover, if $B = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}$, then $G_{I_1^+}(B) = \{x_1\}$ and $G_{I_1^-}(B) = \emptyset$ from Definition 8. According to Theorem 6, we get

$$G_{I_1^+}(B) \cap G_{I_1^-}(B) = \{x_1\} \cap \emptyset = \emptyset.$$

Finally, according to Corollary 7, we can check that $B_{0.6}(X, Y, I_1^+)$ and $B_{0.6}(X, Y, I_1^-)$ do not have concepts in common, except (\emptyset, Y_J) . Indeed,

$$B_{0.6}(X, Y, I_1^+) = \{(\{x_1, 0.8/x_2, 0.6/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}\}), (\{0.6/x_1\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}), (\emptyset, Y_J)\};$$

$$B_{0.6}(X, Y, I_1^-) = \{(\{x_1, 0.7/x_2, 0.6/x_3\}, \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}\}), (\{0.6/x_3\}, \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}, y_{C_6}\}), (\emptyset, Y_J)\}.$$

More in general, the operators $F_{I_1^+}$ and $F_{I_1^-}$ transform a pair of non-disjoint sets of objects into a pair of disjoint sets of attributes when $T > \frac{1}{2}$.

Theorem 7. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$, then $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') = \emptyset$, for each $A, A' \subseteq X$ such that $A \cap A' \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Let $\bar{x} \in A \cap A'$. If $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^+}(A)$, then $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \geq T$ from Definition 8. Moreover, $T > \frac{1}{2}$ by hypothesis. Hence, $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) > \frac{1}{2}$. Since $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ are contraries from Theorem 4 (a), the equation $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \otimes I_1^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) = 0$ must be true. This means that $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) + I_1^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \leq 1$ from Definition 1. Therefore, the inequalities $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) > \frac{1}{2}$ and $I_1^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) + I_1^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \leq 1$ imply that $I_1^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) < \frac{1}{2}$. Then, using Definition 8 again, we can conclude that $\bar{y} \notin F_{I_1^-}(A')$.

Symmetrically, we can immediately prove that if “ $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^-}(A')$ then $\bar{y} \notin F_{I_1^+}(A)$ ”.

Finally, $F_{I_1^+}(A)$ and $F_{I_1^-}(A')$ must be disjoint. \square

Dually, the operators $G_{I_1^+}$ and $G_{I_1^-}$ transform a pair of non-disjoint sets of attributes into a pair of disjoint sets of objects when $T > \frac{1}{2}$.

Theorem 8. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$, then $G_{I_1^+}(B) \cap G_{I_1^-}(B') = \emptyset$, for each $B, B' \subseteq Y_J$ such that $B \cap B' \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. The thesis follows from the contrariety of $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_1^-}$ (see Theorem 4 (a)) and from Definition 8. The proof steps are analogous to those of the previous theorem, and so, they are omitted. \square

As a consequence of Theorems 7 and 8, the following correspondence holds between the fuzzy concepts of $B_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $B_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$ when $T > \frac{1}{2}$.

Corollary 8. Let $T > \frac{1}{2}$,

- (a) if $A \cap A' \neq \emptyset$, then $B \cap B' = \emptyset$;
- (b) if $B \cap B' \neq \emptyset$, then $A \cap A' = \emptyset$;

for each $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$.

Proof. The thesis immediately follows from Theorems 7 and 8. \square

Example 12. Let us go back to Example 11. If $A = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and $A' = \{x_1, x_3\}$, then $F_{I_1^+}(A) = \{y_{C_1}\}$ and $F_{I_1^-}(A') = \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}\}$ from Definition 8. Thus, in line with Theorem 7, we have

$$F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') = \{y_{C_1}\} \cap \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_6}\} = \emptyset.$$

Furthermore, if $B = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}$ and $B' = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}$, then $G_{I_1^+}(B) = \{x_1\}$ and $G_{I_1^-}(B') = \emptyset$ from Definition 8. Hence, in line with Theorem 8, we have

$$G_{I_1^+}(B) \cap G_{I_1^-}(B') = \{x_1\} \cap \emptyset = \emptyset.$$

Lastly, taking into account the fuzzy concepts

$$(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_{0.6}(X, Y_J, I_1^+) \text{ and } (\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_{0.6}(X, Y_J, I_1^-), \text{ where}$$

$(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) = (\{x_1, 0.8/x_2, 0.6/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}\})$ and $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') = (\{0.6/x_3\}, \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}, y_{C_6}\})$, we can observe that $A \cap A' = \{x_3\}$. Thus, according to Corollary 8, $B \cap B' = \{y_{C_1}\} \cap \{y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}, y_{C_6}\} = \emptyset$.

The following results hold for each $T \in (0, 1]$ and connect the truth degrees of the elements of fuzzy sets of objects that are obtained by applying the operators $F_{I_1^+}$ and $F_{I_1^-}$.

Theorem 9. Let $A, A' \subseteq X$ such that $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') \neq \emptyset$, then

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0, \text{ for each } x \in X.$$

Proof. Let $x \in X$.

If $x \notin A$ or $x \notin A'$, then $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) = 0$ and $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0$ by (3). In this case, it is trivial that $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0$.⁹

Suppose that $x \in A \cap A'$. By (3),

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq I_1^+(x, y), \text{ for each } y \in F_{I_1^+}(A) \tag{16}$$

and

$$\varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) \leq I_1^-(x, y), \text{ for each } y \in F_{I_1^-}(A'). \tag{17}$$

Let $z \in F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A')$ (notice that z exists because $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') \neq \emptyset$ from hypothesis), then

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq I_1^+(x, z) \text{ and } \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) \leq I_1^-(x, z), \tag{18}$$

from (16) and (17).

By Theorem 1 (I), the inequalities of (18) imply that $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) \leq I_1^+(x, z) \otimes I_1^-(x, z)$. By Theorem 7 (a), $I_1^+(x, z) \otimes I_1^-(x, z) = 0$. Then, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0$. \square

As a consequence of Theorem 9, the following correspondence holds between the fuzzy concepts of $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$.

Corollary 9. Let $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and let $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$ such that $B \cap B' \neq \emptyset$. Then,

⁹ In the Łukasiewicz algebra, $a \otimes 0 = 0$ for each $a \in [0, 1]$.

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0 \text{ for each } x \in X.$$

Proof. The thesis is an immediate consequence of the previous theorem. In fact, by Definition 10 and by hypothesis, $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') \neq \emptyset$. Then, by Theorem 9, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0$ for each $x \in X$. \square

Example 13. We consider the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) defined in Example 9 and we choose $T = 0.4$. Thus, I_1^+ and I_1^- are defined by Tables 6 and 7.

If $A = A' = \{x_1\}$, then

$$F_{I_1^+}(A) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\} \text{ and } F_{I_1^-}(A') = \{y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}, y_{C_6}, y_{C_7}, y_{C_8}\}$$

from Definition 8. We can observe that $F_{I_1^+}(A) \cap F_{I_1^-}(A') = \{y_{C_3}, y_{C_7}\}$, which is non-empty. Thus, in line with Theorem 9, we get

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_3) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_3) = 0.5 \otimes 0.4 = 0.$$

Of course, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x) = 0$, for all $x \in \{x_1, x_2\}$. This is because $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_1)$, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_2)$, $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_1)$, and $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_2)$ are equal to 0 by (3).

Now, let us focus on the collections of the fuzzy concepts that are extracted from (X, Y_J, I_1^+) and (X, Y_J, I_1^-) with $T = 0.4$:

$$B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_1^+) = \{(\{0.6/x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.4/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}), (\{0.5/x_1\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\}), (\{0.4/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}), (\emptyset, Y_J)\}; \quad (19)$$

$$B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_1^-) = \{(\{0.4/x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.5/x_3\}, \{y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}), (\{0.4/x_1\}, \{y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}), (\{0.4/x_3\}, \{y_{C_2}, y_{C_4}, \dots, y_{C_8}\}), (\emptyset, Y_J)\}. \quad (20)$$

Let $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') \in B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$, where $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) = (\{0.5/x_1\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\})$ and $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A'), B') = (\{0.4/x_1\}, \{y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}, \dots, y_{C_8}\})$. Then, we can see that $B \cap B' = \{y_{C_3}, y_{C_7}\}$. Hence, according to Corollary 9, we get $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_1) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_1) = 0.5 \otimes 0.4 = 0$, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_2) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_2) = 0 \otimes 0 = 0$, and $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x_3) \otimes \varphi_{I_1^-}(A')(x_3) = 0 \otimes 0 = 0$.

5.2. Implications of the relations of sub-contrary

The operators $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}$ and $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}$ transform a set of objects into sets of attributes that are included one in the other when $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+$ and $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-$ satisfy a particular condition. Concerning the results shown in this subsection, we assume that $T \in (0, 1]$.

Theorem 10. Let $A \subseteq X$ such that “ $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in A$ and for each $y \in F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A)$ ”, then $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A) \subseteq F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}(A)$.

Proof. When $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A) = \emptyset$, the thesis holds trivially.

Suppose that $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A) \neq \emptyset$ and consider $\bar{y} \in F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A)$. Then, by Definition 8, $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, \bar{y}) \geq T$, for each $x \in A$. Consequently, using the hypothesis, we have

$$T \leq I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, \bar{y}) \leq \frac{1}{2}, \text{ for each } x \in A. \quad (21)$$

(Notice that the assumptions “ $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A) \neq \emptyset$ ” and “ $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in A$ and $y \in F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A)$ ” imply that T must be less than or equal to $\frac{1}{2}$.) Moreover, by Theorem 4 (b), $P_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}$ and $P_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}$ are sub-contrary. By Definition 6, it is true that $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, \bar{y}) \oplus I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-(x, \bar{y}) = 1$, for each $x \in A$. Hence, by Definition 1,

$$I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+(x, \bar{y}) + I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-(x, \bar{y}) \geq 1, \text{ for each } x \in A. \quad (22)$$

Therefore, by (21) and (22), $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-(x, \bar{y}) \geq \frac{1}{2}$. Finally, the latter inequality, together with (21) implies that $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-(x, \bar{y}) \geq T$ for each $x \in A$. Thus, $\bar{y} \in F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}(A)$ from Definition 8. \square

Theorem 11. Let $A \subseteq X$ such that “ $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in A$ and for each $y \in F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}(A)$ ”, then $F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-}(A) \subseteq F_{I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+}(A)$.

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Theorem 10; in particular, it is immediately obtained by exchanging the role of $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^+$ and $I_{\frac{1}{3}}^-$. \square

Table 12
The fuzzy relation $I_{\exists}^+ : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0,1]$ with $T = 0.2$.

I_{\exists}^+	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}
x_1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0	0.2	0
x_2	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2
x_3	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4

As a consequence of Theorems 10 and 11, we can find a correspondence between the fuzzy concepts of $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$, when I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- satisfy a particular condition.

Corollary 10. Let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$.

- (a) If “ $I_{\exists}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, for each $x \in A$ and for each $y \in Y_J$ ”, then $B \subseteq B'$.
- (b) If “ $I_{\exists}^-(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, for each $x \in A$ and for each $y \in Y_J$ ”, then $B' \subseteq B$.

Proof. (a) By Definition 10, $B = F_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)$ and $B' = F_{I_{\exists}^-}(A)$. Hence, the thesis follows from Theorem 10.

(b) Similarly to item (a), by Definition 10, $B = F_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)$ and $B' = F_{I_{\exists}^-}(A)$. Consequently, the thesis follows from Theorem 11. \square

Dually, the operators $G_{I_{\exists}^+}$ and $G_{I_{\exists}^-}$ transform a set of attributes into sets of objects that are included one in the other when I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- satisfy a particular condition.

Theorem 12. Let $B \subseteq Y_J$ such that “ $I_{\exists}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $y \in B$ and for each $x \in G_{I_{\exists}^+}(B)$ ”, then $G_{I_{\exists}^+}(B) \subseteq G_{I_{\exists}^-}(B)$.

Proof. The proof is dual to that of Theorem 10, so it is omitted. \square

Theorem 13. Let $B \subseteq Y_J$ such that “ $I_{\exists}^-(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $y \in B$ and for each $x \in G_{I_{\exists}^-}(B)$ ”, then $G_{I_{\exists}^-}(B) \subseteq G_{I_{\exists}^+}(B)$.

Proof. The proof is dual to that of Theorem 11, so it is omitted. \square

As a consequence of Theorems 12 and 13, we can find another correspondence between the fuzzy concepts of $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$, when I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- satisfy a particular condition.

Corollary 11. Let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A'), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$.

- (a) If “ $I_{\exists}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, for each $y \in B$ and for each $x \in X$ ”, then $A \subseteq A'$.
- (b) If “ $I_{\exists}^-(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, for each $y \in B$ and for each $x \in X$ ”, then $A' \subseteq A$.

Proof. (a) By Definition 10, $A = G_{I_{\exists}^+}(B)$ and $A' = G_{I_{\exists}^-}(B)$. Hence, the thesis follows from Theorem 12.

(b) In the same way, by Definition 10, $A = G_{I_{\exists}^+}(B)$ and $A' = G_{I_{\exists}^-}(B)$. Consequently, the thesis follows from Theorem 13. \square

Example 14. We consider the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) defined in Example 9 (thus, $(X, Y, Z), (Z, W, J)$, and $r : X \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are represented by Tables 3 and 4, respectively). Here, we choose $T = 0.2$. Then, $\mathcal{B}_{0,2}(Z, W, J)$ is made of the following fuzzy concepts:

- $C_1 = (\{0.5/z_1, 0.8/z_2, 0.2/z_3\}, \{w_3\});$
- $C_2 = (\{0.5/z_1, 0.2/z_3\}, \{w_2, w_3\});$
- $C_3 = (\{0.8/z_2, 0.2/z_3\}, \{w_3, w_4\});$
- $C_4 = (\{0.3/z_2\}, \{w_1, w_3, w_4\});$
- $C_5 = (\{0.2/z_3\}, \{w_2, w_3, w_4\});$
- $C_6 = (\emptyset, \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}).$

The fuzzy relations I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- on $X \times Y_J$ are defined by Tables 12 and 13.

Table 13
The fuzzy relation $I_{\exists}^- : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0.1]$ with $T = 0.2$.

I_{\exists}^-	y_{C_1}	y_{C_2}	y_{C_3}	y_{C_4}	y_{C_5}	y_{C_6}
x_1	0.8	0.8	0.8	1	0.8	1
x_2	0.7	0.7	1	1	1	1
x_3	0.5	0.6	1	1	1	1

We consider the set of objects $\{x_1, x_2\} \subseteq X$, then we get $F_{I_{\exists}^+}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}$ and $F_{I_{\exists}^-}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = Y_J$. We can observe that the hypothesis of Theorem 10 is satisfied: $I_{\exists}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in \{x_1, x_2\}$ and for each $y \in \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}$. Moreover, as stated by Theorem 10, it is true that $F_{I_{\exists}^+}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}$ is included in $F_{I_{\exists}^-}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = Y_J$.

Now, we deal with the fuzzy concepts $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}), \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\})$ and $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}), Y_J)$ of $\mathcal{B}_{0.2}(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}_{0.2}(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$, respectively. Notice that the hypothesis of Corollary 10 is satisfied: $I_{\exists}^+(x, y) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for each $x \in \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ and for each $y \in Y_J$. Therefore, we have $\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\} \subseteq Y_J$.

The following theorem exhibits a connection between the truth degrees of the elements of fuzzy sets of objects that are obtained by applying the operators $F_{I_{\exists}^+}$ and $F_{I_{\exists}^-}$ when a special condition is satisfied.

Theorem 14. Let $A, A' \subseteq X$ such that $A \cap A' \neq \emptyset$ and let $\bar{x} \in A \cap A'$. If

$$\text{“there exists } \bar{y} \in Y_J \text{ with } \varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \text{ and } \varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A')(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y})\text{”},$$

then

$$\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(\bar{x}) \oplus \varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A')(\bar{x}) = 1.$$

Proof. By Theorem 4 (b), the predicates $P_{I_{\exists}^+}$ and $P_{I_{\exists}^-}$ are sub-contraries. Thus, by Definition 6, $I_{\exists}^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \oplus I_{\exists}^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) = 1$. Since $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y})$ and $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A')(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y})$ by hypothesis, the thesis holds trivially. \square

The connection shown by Theorem 14 can be extended to the fuzzy concepts related to the fuzzy relations I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- .

Corollary 12. Let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and let $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$, where $A \cap A' \neq \emptyset$. Let $\bar{x} \in A \cap A'$. If

$$\text{“there exists } \bar{y} \in Y_J \text{ with } \varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^+(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \text{ and } \varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A')(\bar{x}) = I_{\exists}^-(\bar{x}, \bar{y})\text{”},$$

then

$$\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(\bar{x}) \oplus \varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A')(\bar{x}) = 1.$$

Proof. The thesis clearly follows from Theorem 14. \square

Example 15. Let us go back to Example 14. Then, the fuzzy relations I_{\exists}^+ and I_{\exists}^- are defined by Tables 12 and 13. Let us focus on the same pair of concepts $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A), \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_5}\}) \in \mathcal{B}_{0.2}(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^+)$ and $(\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A), Y_J) \in \mathcal{B}_{0.2}(X, Y_J, I_{\exists}^-)$, where $A = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$. We can view that $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(x_1) = I_{\exists}^+(x_1, y_{C_1}) = 0.2$ and $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A)(x_1) = I_{\exists}^-(x_1, y_{C_1}) = 0.8$. This means that the hypothesis of Corollary 12 is satisfied by x_1 . Hence, we get $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)(x_1) \oplus \varphi_{I_{\exists}^-}(A)(x_1) = 0.2 \oplus 0.8 = 1$.

5.3. Implications of the relations of sub-alternation and contradictory

5.3.1. Relations of sub-alternation

The operators $F_{I_1^+}$ and $F_{I_{\exists}^+}$ transform a given set of objects into sets of attributes that are one included in the other. Dually, the operators $G_{I_1^+}$ and $G_{I_{\exists}^+}$ transform a given set of attributes into sets of objects that are one included in the other. Moreover, when the sets of attributes obtained by applying $F_{I_1^+}$ and $F_{I_{\exists}^+}$ to a set A of objects coincide, a relationship between the truth degree of the objects w.r.t. $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)$ and $\varphi_{I_{\exists}^+}(A)$ is established.

Theorem 15. Let $A \subseteq X$ and let $B \subseteq Y_J$, then

- (a) $F_{I_1^+}(A) \subseteq F_{I_3^+}(A)$;
- (b) $G_{I_1^+}(B) \subseteq G_{I_3^+}(B)$;
- (c) when $F_{I_1^+}(A) = F_{I_3^+}(A)$, $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^+}(A)(x)$ for each $x \in X$.

Proof. (a) Let $\bar{y} \in F_{I_1^+}(A)$. By Definition 8, $I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) \geq T$ for each $x \in A$. Moreover, by Theorem 4 (c), $P_{I_3^+}$ is sub-altern of $P_{I_1^+}$. Then, by Definition 6, $I_1^+(x, \bar{y}) \leq I_3^+(x, \bar{y})$ for each $x \in A$. Hence, it is easy to understand that $I_3^+(x, \bar{y}) \geq T$ for each $x \in A$. Employing Definition 8 again, we can conclude that $\bar{y} \in F_{I_3^+}(A)$.

- (b) The proof is analogous to that of item (a), so it is omitted.
- (c) Let $x \in X$. As explained in the proof of item (a),

$$I_1^+(x, y) \leq I_3^+(x, y), \text{ for each } y \in Y_J \tag{23}$$

(recall that this follows from Theorem 4 (c)). Furthermore, by (3),

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) = \min_{y \in F_{I_1^+}(A)} I_1^+(x, y) \text{ and } \varphi_{I_3^+}(A)(x) = \min_{y \in F_{I_3^+}(A)} I_3^+(x, y), \tag{24}$$

where $F_{I_1^+}(A) = F_{I_3^+}(A)$ from hypothesis. Thus, by (23) and (24), the thesis follows immediately. \square

As a consequence of Theorem 15, we can determine a link between the fuzzy concepts of $B_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $B_T(X, Y_J, I_3^+)$.

Corollary 13. Let $(\varphi_{I_1^+}(A), B) \in B_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ and $(\varphi_{I_3^+}(A'), B') \in B_T(X, Y_J, I_3^+)$.

- (a) If $A = A'$, then $B \subseteq B'$;
- (b) if $B = B'$, then $A \subseteq A'$ and $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^+}(A')(x)$ for each $x \in X$.

Proof. (a) By Definition 10, $F_{I_1^+}(A) = B$ and $F_{I_3^+}(A') = B'$. Moreover, $A = A'$ from hypothesis. Thus, by Theorem 15 (a), the inclusion $B \subseteq B'$ must be true.

(b) By Definition 10, $G_{I_1^+}(B) = A'$ and $G_{I_3^+}(B') = A'$. Furthermore, $B = B'$ from hypothesis. Then, by Theorem 15 (b), the inclusion $A \subseteq A'$ must be true.

Now, we consider $x \in X$.

If $x \notin A$, then $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) = 0$ from (3). Consequently, the inequality $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^+}(A')(x)$ trivially holds.

Suppose that $x \in A$. Then, as shown above, $A \subseteq A'$, thus x must belong to A' too. In addition, using Definition 10 again, we know that $F_{I_1^+}(A) = B$ and $F_{I_3^+}(A') = B'$. Hence, by hypothesis $F_{I_1^+}(A) = F_{I_3^+}(A')$. In addition, recall that by (3),

$$\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) = \min_{y \in F_{I_1^+}(A)} I_1^+(x, y) \text{ and } \varphi_{I_3^+}(A')(x) = \min_{y \in F_{I_3^+}(A')} I_3^+(x, y). \tag{25}$$

Lastly, by (23) (see the proof of Theorem 15) and by (25), we obtain $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^+}(A')(x)$. \square

Example 16. Let us focus on the fuzzy relational context family (\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}) defined in Example 9. Then, the fuzzy relations I_1^+ and I_3^+ are defined by Tables 6 and 8.

By Definition 8, we find $F_{I_1^+}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}$ and $F_{I_3^+}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\}$. Consequently, according to Theorem 15 (a), the inequality $F_{I_1^+}(\{x_1, x_2\}) \subseteq F_{I_3^+}(\{x_1, x_2\})$ is satisfied.

Employing Definition 8 again, $G_{I_1^+}(\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}) = \{x_3\}$ and $G_{I_3^+}(\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}) = \{x_2, x_3\}$. So, according to Theorem 15(b) $G_{I_1^+}(\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\}) \subseteq G_{I_3^+}(\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}\})$.

Now, we consider $\{x_1\} \subseteq X$. Then,

$$F_{I_1^+}(\{x_1\}) = F_{I_3^+}(\{x_1\}) = \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\}.$$

Additionally, by (3), $\varphi_{I_1^+}(\{x_1\})(x_1) = 0.5$ and $\varphi_{I_3^+}(\{x_1\})(x_1) = 0.6$. Hence, according to Theorem 15 (c), $\varphi_{I_1^+}(\{x_1\})(x_1) \leq \varphi_{I_3^+}(\{x_1\})(x_1)$.

Regarding the fuzzy concepts related to I_1^+ and I_3^+ , $B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_1^+)$ is given by (19) and

$$B_{0.4}(X, Y_J, I_3^+) = \{(\{0.6/x_1, 0.5/x_2, 0.4/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_7}\}), (\{0.5/x_2, 0.4/x_3\}, \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_2}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}, y_{C_7}\}), (\{0.4/x_3\}, Y_J)\}.$$

In particular, let us take into account

$$(\varphi_{I_1^+}(\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}), \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\}) \text{ and } (\varphi_{I_1^+}(\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}), \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}\}),$$

where $\{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}\} \subseteq \{y_{C_1}, y_{C_3}, y_{C_4}, y_{C_5}\}$, in line with Corollary 13.

In what follows, we connect the pairs of operators $(F_{I_1^-}, G_{I_1^-})$ and $(F_{I_3^-}, G_{I_3^-})$, as well as their corresponding fuzzy concepts through the relation of sub-alternation between $P_{I_1^-}$ and $P_{I_3^-}$.

Theorem 16. Let $A \subseteq X$ and let $B \subseteq Y_J$, then

- (a) $F_{I_1^-}(A) \subseteq F_{I_3^-}(A)$;
- (b) $G_{I_1^-}(B) \subseteq G_{I_3^-}(B)$;
- (c) when $F_{I_1^-}(A) = F_{I_3^-}(A)$, $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^-}(A)(x)$ for each $x \in X$.

Proof. The proof follows from Theorem 4 (d); it can be easily obtained from the proof of Theorem 15 by exchanging I_1^+ with I_1^- and I_3^+ with I_3^- . \square

Corollary 14. Let $(\varphi_{I_1^-}(A), B) \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-)$ and $(\varphi_{I_3^-}(A'), B') \in \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_3^-)$.

- (a) If $A = A'$, then $B \subseteq B'$;
- (b) if $B = B'$, then $A \subseteq A'$ and $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A)(x) \leq \varphi_{I_3^-}(A')(x)$ for each $x \in X$.

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Corollary 13 and follows from Theorem 16. \square

5.3.2. Relation of contradictory

In what follows, we discover that the pairs of operators $(F_{I_1^+}, G_{I_1^+})$ and $(F_{\neg I_3^-}, G_{\neg I_3^-})$, as well as $(F_{I_1^-}, G_{I_1^-})$ and $(F_{\neg I_3^+}, G_{\neg I_3^+})$, coincide. This implies that the same fuzzy concepts are generated from I_1^+ and $\neg I_3^-$, as well as from I_1^- and $\neg I_3^+$. Recall that if $I : X \times Y_J \rightarrow [0, 1]$, then $\neg I(x, y) = 1 - I(x, y)$ for each $x \in X$ and $y \in Y_J$.

Theorem 17. Let $A \subseteq X$ and let $B \subseteq Y_J$, then

- (a) $F_{I_1^+}(A) = F_{\neg I_3^-}(A)$;
- (b) $G_{I_1^+}(B) = G_{\neg I_3^-}(B)$;
- (c) $\varphi_{I_1^+}(A) = \varphi_{\neg I_3^-}(A)$.

Proof. By Theorem 4 (e), $P_{I_1^+}$ and $P_{I_3^-}$ are contradictories. Thus, by Definition 6, $I_1^+ = \neg I_3^-$. Consequently, the thesis trivially follows. \square

Corollary 15. Let $T \in (0, 1]$, then $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^+) = \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, \neg I_3^-)$.

Proof. The thesis is an immediate consequence of Definitions 8 and 10, and Theorem 17. \square

Theorem 18. Let $A \subseteq X$ and let $B \subseteq Y_J$, then

- (a) $F_{I_1^-}(A) = F_{\neg I_3^+}(A)$;
- (b) $G_{I_1^-}(B) = G_{\neg I_3^+}(B)$;
- (c) $\varphi_{I_1^-}(A) = \varphi_{\neg I_3^+}(A)$.

Proof. By Theorem 4 (f), $P_{I_1^-}$ and $P_{I_3^+}$ are contradictories. Thus, by Definition 6, $I_1^- = \neg I_3^+$. Consequently, the thesis trivially follows. \square

Corollary 16. Let $T \in (0, 1]$, then $\mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, I_1^-) = \mathcal{B}_T(X, Y_J, \neg I_3^+)$.

Proof. The thesis is an immediate consequence of Definitions 8 and 10, and Theorem 18. \square

6. Conclusions and future directions

Our findings make a two-part contribution to the progress of Aristotle's square. Specifically, they unveil a novel understanding of the square of opposition within the context of Fuzzy Relational Concept Analysis, highlighting its usefulness as a valuable instrument for data analysis. In particular, the logical relations among quantifiers allow us to understand the effects of employing different FRCA quantifiers on fuzzy concepts.

In the future, we plan to expand this work by investigating the logical relations among other fuzzy quantifiers and by constructing novel structures of opposition within the FRCA framework. Thus, we will focus on the positive and negative t-scaling quantifiers introduced in [44] and [50], which generalize the positive and negative universal quantifiers studied in this paper. Let A and B be fuzzy sets of a finite universe X , if S_t and S_t^- respectively denote the positive and negative quantifiers determined by the threshold $t \in [0, 1]$, then the values $S_t(A, B)$ and $S_t^-(A, B)$ are the truth degrees of "there exists a part of A so that all its elements are in B and its size is at least as large as t (in the scale $[0,1]$) w.r.t. the size of A " and "there exists a part of A so that all its elements are not in B and its size is at least as large as t (in the scale $[0,1]$) w.r.t. the size of A ". If I_t and I_s^- denote the fuzzy relations generated by the t-scaling quantifiers S_t and S_s^- with $t, s \in [0, 1]$, we intend to discover the real intervals $[t_1, t_2], [s_1, s_2] \subseteq [0, 1]$ so that I_t and I_s^- are contraries for each $t \in [t_1, t_2]$ and $s \in [s_1, s_2]$. Analogously, we are interested in determining $[t_1^+, t_2^+], [t_1^-, t_2^-] \subseteq [0, 1]$ so that I_{\exists}^+ is sub-altern of I_t^+ and I_{\exists}^- is sub-altern of $I_{t^*}^-$ for each $t \in [t_1^+, t_2^+]$ and $t^* \in [t_1^-, t_2^-]$. Eventually, we could analyze how the thresholds t (for constructing a t-scaling quantifier) and T (for constructing fuzzy concepts) are connected, for example, by finding under which conditions (t_1, T_1) and (t_2, T_2) generate the same collection of fuzzy concepts. Additionally, we will explore the implications of the logical relations on fuzzy concepts obtained through other approaches in the literature. Certainly, we will delve deeper into the potential applications of the results of Section 5 to data analysis in the fuzzy setting.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefania Boffa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Petra Murinová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Stefania Boffa reports financial support and article publishing charges were provided by University of Ostrava. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This article has been produced with the financial support of the study of the project "Research of Excellence on Digital Technologies and Wellbeing" CZ.02.01.01/00/22-008/0004583 which is co-financed by the European Union.

The work was also supported from ERDF/ESF by the project "Centre for the development of Artificial Intelligence Methods for the Automotive Industry of the region" No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/17-049/0008414.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Laurent Miclet, Henri Prade, Analogical proportions and square of oppositions, in: Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems: 15th International Conference, IPMU 2014, in: 15-19, 2014, Proceedings, Part II 15, Springer, Montpellier, France, July 2014, pp. 324–334.
- [2] Régis Pellissier, "Setting" n-opposition, Log. Univers. 2 (2) (2008) 235–263.
- [3] Terence Parsons, Things that are right with the traditional square of opposition, Log. Univers. 2 (1) (2008) 3–11.
- [4] Philip Peterson, Intermediate Quantities: Logic, Linguistics and Aristotelian Semantics, Routledge, 2020.
- [5] Terence Parsons, The traditional square of opposition, 1997.
- [6] Dorit Abusch, Mats Rooth, Empty-domain effects for presuppositional and non-presuppositional determiners, in: Context-Dependence in the Analysis of Linguistic Meaning, Brill, 2002, pp. 7–27.
- [7] Alessio Moretti, Why the logical hexagon?, Log. Univers. 6 (1–2) (2012) 69–107.
- [8] Jean-Yves Béziau, The power of the hexagon, Log. Univers. 6 (2012) 1–43.
- [9] Stephen Read, John Buridan's theory of consequence and his octagons of opposition, in: Around and Beyond the Square of Opposition, Springer, 2012, pp. 93–110.
- [10] Lorenz Demey, Hans Smessaert, Aristotelian and duality relations beyond the square of opposition, in: Diagrammatic Representation and Inference: 10th International Conference, Diagrams 2018, Edinburgh, UK, June 18-22, 2018, Proceedings 10, Springer, 2018, pp. 640–656.
- [11] Alessio Moretti, Geometry of modalities? Yes: through n-opposition theory, Trav. Log. 17 (2004) 102–145.
- [12] John Venn, Jn Keynes, studies and exercises in formal logic, Mind 9 (a) (1884).
- [13] Davide Ciucci, Didier Dubois, Henri Prade, Oppositions in rough set theory, in: International Conference on Rough Sets and Knowledge Technology, Springer, 2012, pp. 504–513.

- [14] Didier Dubois, Henri Prade, From Blanché's hexagonal organization of concepts to formal concept analysis and possibility theory, *Log. Univers.* 6 (1) (2012) 149–169.
- [15] Niki Pfeifer, Giuseppe Sanfilippo, Probabilistic squares and hexagons of opposition under coherence, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 88 (2017) 282–294.
- [16] Didier Dubois, Henri Prade, Agnes Rico, Graded cubes of opposition and possibility theory with fuzzy events, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 84 (2017) 168–185.
- [17] Roberto Abbruzzese, Angelo Gaeta, Vincenzo Loia, Luigi Lomasto, Francesco Orciuoli, Detecting influential news in online communities: an approach based on hexagons of opposition generated by three-way decisions and probabilistic rough sets, *Inf. Sci.* 578 (2021) 364–377.
- [18] Stefania Boffa, Davide Ciucci, Petra Murinová, Comparing hexagons of opposition in probabilistic rough set theory, in: *International Conference on Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems*, Springer, 2022, pp. 622–633.
- [19] Didier Dubois, Henri Prade, Gradual structures of oppositions, in: *Enric Trillas: A Passion for Fuzzy Sets: A Collection of Recent Works on Fuzzy Logic*, 2015, pp. 79–91.
- [20] Petra Murinová, Vilém Novák, Analysis of generalized square of opposition with intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 242 (2014) 89–113.
- [21] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Graded generalized hexagon in fuzzy natural logic, in: *Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 611, 2016, pp. 36–47.
- [22] Petra Murinová, Vilém Novák, The theory of intermediate quantifiers in fuzzy natural logic revisited and the model of “many”, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 388 (2020) 56–89.
- [23] Stefania Boffa, Petra Murinová, Vilém Novák, Graded polygons of opposition in fuzzy formal concept analysis, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 132 (2021) 128–153.
- [24] Stefania Boffa, Petra Murinová, Vilém Novák, Petr Ferbas, Graded cubes of opposition in fuzzy formal concept analysis, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 145 (2022) 187–209.
- [25] Bernhard Ganter, Rudolf Wille, *Formal Concept Analysis: Mathematical Foundations*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [26] Rudolf Wille, Restructuring lattice theory: an approach based on hierarchies of concepts, in: *Formal Concept Analysis: 7th International Conference, ICFA 2009*, in: 21–24, 2009 Proceedings 7, Springer, Darmstadt, Germany, May 2009, pp. 314–339.
- [27] Rudolf Wille, *Begriffsdenken: Von der griechischen philosophie bis zur künstlichen intelligenz heute*, 2001.
- [28] Damian, A. Tamburri, Design principles for the general data protection regulation (gdpr): a formal concept analysis and its evaluation, *Inf. Syst.* 91 (2020) 101469.
- [29] Jirapond Muangprathub, Siriwan Kajornkasirat, Apirat Wanichsombat, Document plagiarism detection using a new concept similarity in formal concept analysis, *J. Appl. Math.* 2021 (2021) 1–10.
- [30] Ahmed Abid, Mohsen Rouached, Nizar Messai, Semantic web service composition using semantic similarity measures and formal concept analysis, *Multimed. Tools Appl.* 79 (2020) 6569–6597.
- [31] Manuel Ojeda-Hernández, Domingo López-Rodríguez, Ángel Mora, Lexicon-based sentiment analysis in texts using formal concept analysis, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 155 (2023) 104–112.
- [32] Bernhard Ganter, Gerd Stumme, Rudolf Wille, *Formal Concept Analysis: Foundations and Applications*, vol. 3626, Springer, 2005.
- [33] Carmen De Maio, Giuseppe Fenza, Vincenzo Loia, Sabrina Senatore, Towards an automatic fuzzy ontology generation, in: *2009 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems, IEEE*, 2009, pp. 1044–1049.
- [34] Stefania Boffa, Carmen De Maio, Antonio Di Nola, Giuseppe Fenza, Anna Rita Ferraioli, Vincenzo Loia, Unifying fuzzy concept lattice construction methods, in: *2016 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE)*, IEEE, 2016, pp. 209–216.
- [35] Marianne Huchard, Cyril Roume, Petko Valtchev, When concepts point at other concepts: the case of uml diagram reconstruction, in: *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Advances in Formal Concept Analysis for Knowledge Discovery in Databases (FCAKDD)*, 2002, pp. 32–43.
- [36] Marianne Huchard, Relational concept analysis (rca), *Ann. Math. Artif. Intell.* 67 (2013) 81–108.
- [37] Mohamed Rouane Hacene, Amedeo Napoli, Petko Valtchev, Yannick Toussaint, Rokia Bendaoud, Ontology learning from text using relational concept analysis, in: *2008 International MCETECH Conference on e-Technologies (Mcetech 2008)*, IEEE, 2008, pp. 154–163.
- [38] Patricia Mateiu, Adrian Groza, Cristina Nica, Learning ontologies with relational concept analysis, in: *2022 IEEE 20th Jubilee World Symposium on Applied Machine Intelligence and Informatics (SAMII)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 000219–000224.
- [39] M. Farida Begam, Domain ontology construction using formal concept and relational concept analysis, in: *2021 2nd Global Conference for Advancement in Technology (GCAT)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–9.
- [40] Jessie Carbonnel, Marianne Huchard, Clémentine Nebut, Exploring the variability of interconnected product families with relational concept analysis, in: *Proceedings of the 23rd International Systems and Software Product Line Conference-Volume B*, 2019, pp. 199–206.
- [41] Nicolas Hlad, Bérénice Lemoine, Marianne Huchard, Abdelhak-Djamel Seriai, Leveraging relational concept analysis for automated feature location in software product lines, in: *Proceedings of the 20th ACM SIGPLAN International Conference on Generative Programming: Concepts and Experiences*, 2021, pp. 170–183.
- [42] Mickaël Wajnberg, Petko Valtchev, Alexandre Blondin Massé, Abderrahim Benmoussa, Maja Krajcinovic, Caroline Laverdière, Emile Levy, Daniel Sinnett, Valérie Marcil, Mining heterogeneous associations from pediatric cancer data by relational concept analysis, in: *2020 International Conference on Data Mining Workshops (ICDMW)*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 597–604.
- [43] Stefania Boffa, Petra Murinová, Vilém Novák, A proposal to extend relational concept analysis with fuzzy scaling quantifiers, *Knowl.-Based Syst.* 231 (2021) 107452.
- [44] Stefania Boffa, Extracting concepts from fuzzy relational context families, *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Syst.* 31 (4) (2023) 1202–1213.
- [45] Vilém Novák, A formal theory of intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (10) (2008) 1229–1246.
- [46] Vilém Novák, Irina Perfilieva, Antonin Dvorak, *Insight into Fuzzy Modeling*, John Wiley & Sons, 2016.
- [47] Vilém Novák, Fuzzy logic theory of evaluating expressions and comparative quantifiers, in: *Proc. 11th Int. Conf. IPMU*, Paris, vol. 2, 2006, pp. 1572–1579.
- [48] Vilém Novák, A comprehensive theory of trichotomous evaluative linguistic expressions, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (22) (2008) 2939–2969.
- [49] Stefania Boffa, Brunella Gerla, An analysis of frca quantifiers, in: *Conference of the European Society for Fuzzy Logic and Technology*, Springer, 2023, pp. 405–416.
- [50] Stefania Boffa, Petra Murinová, Logical relations between t-scaling quantifiers and their implications in fuzzy relational concept analysis, in: *Conference of the European Society for Fuzzy Logic and Technology*, Springer, 2023, pp. 393–404.
- [51] Radim Bělohlávek, *Fuzzy Relational Systems: Foundations and Principles*, vol. 20, Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [52] Silke Pollandt, *Fuzzy-Begriffe: Formale Begriffsanalyse unscharfer Daten*, Springer-Verlag, 2013.
- [53] Radim Bělohlávek, Fuzzy Galois connections, *Math. Log. Q.* 45 (4) (1999) 497–504.
- [54] Agnès Braud, Xavier Dolques, Marianne Huchard, Florence Le Ber, Generalization effect of quantifiers in a classification based on relational concept analysis, *Knowl.-Based Syst.* 160 (2018) 119–135.